

Volume XLVIII / No. 1 / August 2024

MASIHI SEVAK

A Journal of Christian Ministry

THE UNITED THEOLOGICAL COLLEGE
Bengaluru, India.

MASIHI SEVAK

A JOURNAL OF CHRISTIAN MINISTRY

VOLUME XLVIII/ No. 1

AUGUST 2024

EDITOR

Rev. Dr. Jeeva Kumar Ravela

Masihi Sevak accepts articles, sermons and reports about
Christian Ministry for publication. Write to:

The Editor

masihisevak@gmail.com

Inviting articles, sermons, reflections regarding various aspects of Christian Ministry for the forthcoming issue. Contributions can be addressed to the Editor, masihisevak@gmail.com

Contents

Editorialv

I. Articles

1. The Web of Life: Psalm 104's Portrayal of Ecological Interdependence in the Anthropocene Era
Mede Jeevan Sagar 1

2. The Nature and Calling of the Church in India Today
Ben Jonathan Immanuel..... 11

3. John Wesley Theology of Covenant: A Foundation for Servant Living
F. Lal Chhandama 23

4. Divine Empathy and Human Apathy: The Case of Jonah
P D Sengvaidam Chiru 35

5. Mindful Faith: Integrating Mindfulness into Christian Counselling
Akhil A O 43

6. Vulnerability of Sexually Abused Children: Analysis of Just Therapy
Rita Rana..... 51

7. Characteristics of Adolescent Girls: Implications for Pastoral Care and Counselling
L. Anitha 59

II. Biblical Reflections and Sermons

8. Worship that Transforms: A Call to Authenticity and Reverence
Sam T Rajkumar 67

9. Nathaniel, An Enlightened Person: A Reflection
based on John 1:44-51
Johnson Thomaskutty..... 79
10. Sermon on the Mount as a Key to Understanding Jesus’
Social Teachings and Social Justice as a Christian Duty
Jeeva Kumar Ravela..... 85
11. Prophetic Imagination of the Self: Reflection from
Isaiah 11: 1-5; Matthew 8: 28-34
Eyingbeni Humtsoe-Nienu 95
12. Jesus, the Prophet
Ben Das 101
13. The Impact of Restorative Justice on the Welfare
of Victims of Criminal False Accusation
Cases: An Examination of Luke 4:18-19
Praveen Kodiyattil..... 109
- III. Liturgy
14. Liturgy - Theme: The Voice of Silence
Ben Das 121

— Editorial

The current issue of MASIHI SEVAK consists of articles, biblical reflections, sermons and, liturgy, reflecting upon the contextual realities of the Indian church and society. Through their writings, the authors have presented various concerns that the contemporary church is wrestling to find answers considering biblical messages and theological debates. These writings apparently reveal a deeper commitment of the church to engage in the Biblical, theological and, ministerial directions to contemporary realities. They reverberate the ministry of the church from vivid vantage points as significant views to inform the faith communities that innovative readings and reflections are imperative to adopt and practice the diverse ministries of the church for the welfare and wellbeing of humankind. Resources in the form of articles, biblical reflections, and liturgy aim to reflect upon various concerns of the church and society with the theme of social values, social justice and ministry of counselling. I am thankful to the contributors for their profound engagement with the Bible, expounding on relevant theological and ministerial discussions to stimulate the ministries of the church.

The church engages in both spiritual and social activities, upholding values and norms established by the teachings of the Holy Bible. One can assert that there is no distinction between secular, social and spiritual tasks of the church as social concerns

are not outside the purview of spiritual responsibilities. At the same time, the mission and ministry of the Church is to continually enable faith communities to extend their horizon of serving human communities beyond the given notion of service. The ministry of the church is to ensure that she takes a vibrant role in the life of society, analyzing, and discerning the signs of times and, responding to them with appropriate theological and missional schemas. In a society where the life of girl children is always in danger due to various factors, such as patriarchy, male chauvinism, sexual exploitation, and gender discrimination. At this juncture, the ministry of the church is to propose an appropriate missional strategy, and, persuade individuals to become members of the healing ministry. Thus, vulnerable and wounded individuals find hope in the ministry of the church.

We are living in the context of technological innovations, robotic expertise, and the emergence of artificial intelligence. The world has become a global village and is growing faster in all realms of life than ever. Ecological sensitivity that considers the earth as a God-given habitat for all living and non-living beings must be upheld in our perception of the relationship between humankind and living things. A country like India moves through all kinds of realities in terms of socio-economic, religio-cultural, and political changes. Inappropriately, ruling authorities often impose a patriotism culture on the citizens of a country, compelling communities to concur with majoritarian religions and cultures as their core views uphold the dignity and security of the nation. The government eventually decides whether who will become the rightful citizen of the country. There has been a tussle between democratic and fascist forces that presents the unstoppable and unresolved social, cultural, and political struggles of citizens for good governance. The ruling parties continue to emphasize that they want to be keen and proactive in all matters while keeping the interest of the nation

at the forefront. By doing so, they often neglect the freedom of various minority organizations, both religious and cultural, obstructing their establishments, spying on, and intruding into their ministerial activities, and arbitrarily causing damage and disturbance to their functioning. In such a context, the mission and ministry of the church are not only at stake but are also certainly unstable in serving the needs of human communities at large.

At this juncture, it is to reiterate that the mission of God is not only to uplift vulnerable people but also to reform the unjust structures of society according to the salvific plan of God. The Christian responsibility of learning about social justice in a society is a significant factor because it is urgent for the church and faith communities to take up this matter as a matter of spiritual concern. The ministerial strategies of the church need to be framed and reframed considering ongoing unjust activities in the society. The church cannot remain a silent spectator, rather, it must become an active agent of change by being involved in matters concerning life and justice.

Jeeva Kumar Ravela,
Editor

THE WEB OF LIFE: PSALM 104'S PORTRAYAL OF ECOLOGICAL INTERDEPENDENCE IN THE ANTHROPOCENE ERA

Mede Jeevan Sagar*

Introduction

Our planet is on the verge of a catastrophic ecological disaster. The Anthropocene era has created a reckoning with our relationship with nature since, human activity has had a tremendous impact on Earth's systems. It is critical that we reconsider how we perceive our role in the complex web of life as we struggle with the effects of our collective activities. Psalm 104, which honors the divine design of creation, provides a rich framework for examining the human relationship with the animal kingdom and the need to take care of the environment. This essay explores the ecological lessons learned from this ancient text, shedding light on the harmonious balance that keeps life on Earth alive and making us reevaluate our responsibility for protecting the environment that supports numerous species.

* Rev. Dn. Mede Jeevan Sagar is an ordained Deacon of the Church of South India, Diocese of Krishna Godavari, Andhra Pradesh. At present, he teaches the Old Testament at the Bishop's College, Kolkata.

The Anthropocene¹ Era

Psalm 104 connects with Creation theology, but it receives little reflection like the book of Genesis. Based on Genesis, creation's explanation of Human dominion over animals contributed to a new age known as "Anthropocene era" in Earth's history. One of the special hymns in the Hebrew bible that refers to animals is Psalm 104. This ecological picture of creation distinguishes God's care for animals. However, humans appear in the psalm as a separate creature from other creatures in God's creation. A focused reading of Psalm 104 through an ecological lens gives specific attention to animals, and is a helpful ecological framework for reading in the realm of biblical creation theology.

Significant developments have occurred in the last two decades. Scholars, who, study animals mainly associate with their selected areas but now go beyond their traditional areas more frequently in humanities and social sciences, where there is rise in an interdisciplinary study known as "animal studies."² While Genesis informs the concept of human dominion over nature, Psalm 104 offers a different perspective. This psalm portrays a harmonious creation where humans share the earth with other creatures, all dependent on God's care. Through an ecological lens, Psalm 104 provides a valuable framework for understanding creation theology that prioritizes well-being of all living things. The prominence on animals aligns with the rapidly increasing field of animal studies, which emphasizes the

-
- 1 The Anthropocene Era is an unofficial unit of geologic time, used to describe the most recent period in Earth's history when human activity started to have a significant impact on the planet's climate and ecosystems."Anthropocene | NationalGeographicSociety," <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/anthropocene>. Accessed on 2022-09-03 15:29:52.
 - 2 Few scholars who started the animal studies. Matthew Calarco, *Thinking through Animals: Identity, Difference, Indistinction* (California: Stanford University Press, 2015).; Kari Weil, *Thinking Animals: Why Animal Studies Now?* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2012).

importance of considering animal life in our understanding of the world.

By integrating these insights, we can move towards a more holistic and ecological approach to creation theology. Before constructing this argument for Psalm 104, however, it is essential to emphasise the significance of the Anthropocene as a way of describing the present-day context. The concept of the Anthropocene is grounded in debates among scientists that are often quite technical.³ For this argument, it is necessary to note that Anthropocene refers to the understanding that changes in the earth's biogeochemical⁴ systems, which human activities brought. Those activities of humans have become severe enough to begin leaving a trace in the stratigraphic⁵ layers of the planet's crust, which scientists use to categorise earth's history into ages, epochs, and periods. Thus, some scientists hold opinion that human beings live in the Anthropocene era, shaped permanently by changes to earth systems created by humanity (Anthropos).⁶

Although not all of these changes are related to animals, at least two fundamental ways link these changes to human-animal interactions. First, the massive increase in domestic animal products for human consumption across the world causes ecological destruction due to industrial animal agriculture's role in climate change, Deforestation, water pollution, and other issues, as well as the severe suffering of domesticated animals and human labourers, as discussed by many animal studies scholars and labour and animal rights activists.⁷ Second, several human

3 Erle C. Ellis, *Anthropocene: A Very Short Introduction* (United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2018), 110

4 Biogeochemical cycle, "any of the natural pathways by which essential elements of living matter are circulated. The term biogeochemical is a contraction that refers to the consideration of the biological, geological, and chemical aspects of each cycle."; Accessed 2022-09-01 20:57:47.

5 A layer in stratosphere.

6 Ellis, *Anthropocene: A Very Short Introduction*, 113.

7 Anthony John Weis, *The Ecological Hoofprint: The Global Burden of Industrial Livestock* (London: Zed Books, 2013), 26-37.

activities, such as environmental destruction, anthropogenic⁸ climate change, stealing, and other factors, appear to be causing what some call “the sixth great extinction” of animal species. This extinction may be comparable to the mass disappearance events that wiped out non-avian dinosaurs.⁹ Considering the Anthropocene, humanity stands at a crossroads. While Psalm 104 offers a beautiful portrait of God’s creation and our role within it, our actions now significantly impact the natural world. We must reconcile our dominion over creation with the responsibility to care for it, ensuring its flourishing for generations to come. The following is the re-examination of Psalm 104, with a particular emphasis on Animals in the ‘Anthropocene era’.

Human Interdependence with Animals

Psalm 104 contains several animal species in verses 11, 12, 17, 18, 20, 21, 25, and 26.¹⁰ Westermann observed that these verses imply that all animals, including fish and mosquitoes, look to God for food.¹¹ These animals do not depend on other elements of the creation, but on God alone. For example, whereas God may have created waters in the past and put them in their appropriate places (104:8-9), now these waters sustain animals both directly (104:11) and indirectly when they sustain the trees in which birds live and sing (104:12, 16-17). While God created the moon and darkness, combined with sun and light, in the past, non-human animals and humans lived together (104:19- 23). B. Anderson

8 Caused by humans or their activities. “ANTHROPOGENIC Meaning, Definition in Cambridge English Dictionary,” Accessed on 2022-09 0315:33:10, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/anthropogenic>.

9 Elizabeth Kolbert, *The Sixth Extinction: An Unnatural History*, First edition. (New York: Henry Holt and Company, 2014), 87.

10 wild asses (104:11), birds (104:12, 17), including the stork (104:17), cattle or other grass-eating beasts (104:14), mountain goats or ibexes (104:18), hyraxes (104:18), lions (104:21), water animals including the great beast Leviathan (104:26), and, more generally, the “living creatures” of field (104:11), forest (104:20), and sea (104:25).

11 Claus Westermann, *The Living Psalms*, trans. J.R Porter (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1989), 251.

states, “Psalm 104 speaks in intense terms of how animals and humans depend upon God’s grace; humans are all on the same level.”¹² Thus, all parts of creation exist concerning one another.

James L. Mays notes in a brief and beautiful reflection on Psalm 104 that all the foundations of creation “are interrelated in the great web of the works of the Lord.”¹³ Thus, it portrays the environment around us as a “web” of “interdependence” parts that depend on one another rather than surviving as independent beings. Commentators have witnessed the author of Psalm 104, a pre-modern ecologist, witnessing the interdependence of air, soil, water, trees, plants, animals, and humans.¹⁴ In conclusion, Psalm 104 transcends the simple praise of creation and reveals a profound ecological truth: all living things, from the smallest creatures to humankind, are interconnected in a web of dependence on God’s providence. This interdependence extends beyond individual needs, as elements such as water and sunlight support ecosystems. Psalm 104, thus serves as a testament to the convoluted balance and interconnectedness within God’s creation.

This Psalm modifies the roles that humans and animals play. The issue of food provision that the Psalm has addressed simultaneously emphasises how dependent humans are on a good God for their daily needs. In this world, there is excellent interdependence between humans and animals. It is most evident in how humans handle animals for food and work. One should have a deeper understanding of human relationships

12 Bernhard W. Anderson, *From Creation to New Creation: Old Testament Perspectives* (Eugene: Stock Pub, 2005), 32.

13 James L Mays, “Maker of Heaven and Earth’: Creation in the Psalms,” in *God Who Creates: Essays in Honor of W. Sibley Towner*, ed. W. Sibley Towner, William P. Brown, and S. Dean McBride (Grand Rapids: W.B. Eerdmans, 2000), 84.

14 Keck, *The New Interpreter’s Bible*, 4:1099.; Walter Brueggemann and W. H. Bellinger, *Psalms*, NCBC (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2014), 448.

with animals, especially how much they rely on them for companionship, food, and labour.¹⁵

Therefore, let us celebrate the divine Symphony of creation, where humans and animals find sustenance and purpose in their unique roles. May we, ever mindful of God's gracious hand, cultivate a deeper respect for all living creatures, recognizing the profound interdependence woven into the very fabric of life.

Human Destruction of Forest

The created world is portrayed in Psalm 104 as a collection of places and specific times where various animal species are permitted to explore their different ways of living. Psalm 104 shows a variety of environments that can be found on the earth, including the sea or deep (104:3,6-9, 25-26), mountains (104:8, 10, 13, 18), valleys (104:8,10), springs or streams (104:10, 12), trees (104:12, 16-17), fields of grass and other plants (104:14), and rocks (104:18). These environments portray creation in a more fascinating way. Instead, as mentioned above, with references to birds in trees alongside streams, they show the strength of God and provide a home for creatures. Indeed, several of these terrains are referred to as spaces that are "for" animals. God has provided each animal with a particular area to live that is suitable to their needs; this area is appropriately referred to by some biblical scholars as "habitat."¹⁶ In conclusion, Psalm 104 transcends a mere list of locations. It paints a picture of a fastidiously designed world, where diverse environments from the sea's depths to mountain peaks serve not just as a backdrop, but, as providential habitats for a vibrant collage of life. Each creature finds its place and fulfils, its needs met by the Creator's

15 Robert Gnuse, "Psalm 104: The Panorama of Life," *Biblical Theology Bulletin: Journal of Bible and Culture* 51.1 (2021): 9.

16 Patrick D Miller, Jr, "The Poetry of Creation: Psalm 104," in *God Who Creates: Essays in Honor of W. Sibley Towner*, ed. W. Sibley Towner, William P. Brown, and S. Dean McBride (Grand Rapids: W.B. Eerdmans Pub, 2000), 99.

wisdom, reflecting both God’s power and care for God’s creation. However, the presentation highlights the significance of this attention to the place and time of animals.

Today, “place” has become one of the most important considerations among animal studies scholars who focus on matters of destruction.¹⁷ Human environment destruction is one of the leading causes of the increase in endangered species and their extinctions, which are now observed globally. Animals have developed to live not simply in any available space but in particular types of habitats required for animals to meet their species-specific needs. As human populations and development have grown, there is not enough space left for some species to flourish or survive in species-specific ways. Moreover, some animals, such as certain species of birds or sea turtles, are attached not simply to particular environment types. However, specific sites return, for example, to their place of birth to reproduce as humans transform these places for their use (Humans’ Destruction of Forest).

Caring and Protecting: Human Responsibility in Psalm 104

Psalm 104 presents a theocentric rather than an anthropocentric image of creation. Although humans are mentioned in Psalm 104, they are only one of God’s creatures and do not hold any special status. Humans are first mentioned in the second half of v. 14, after “all the living creatures of the field” (104:11a), wild asses (104:11b), birds (104:12), and, cattle or other grass-eating animals (104:14a) have previously appeared. However, this sequence resembles Genesis 1, and because animals appear before humans, Psalm 104 proceeds to nonhuman animals after referring to humans. As Elizabeth Johnson noted in her theological reading

¹⁷ Thom Van Dooren, *Flight Ways: Life and Loss at the Edge of Extinction* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2016), 45–47.

of it, Psalm 104 contains “no trace of a command for human dominion. It is a theocentric portrayal of the world that views as a counterbalance to mastery carried out on the assumption that humans have a right to rule other species.”¹⁸ Psalm 104 presents a theocentric perspective on creation, emphasizing God’s sovereignty rather than human dominion. Humans are mentioned alongside various creatures, highlighting their place in the larger variety of God’s creation. The psalm’s focus on God’s sustaining power and the absence of dominion challenges anthropocentric interpretations that prioritize human dominion over nature.

However, Psalm 104 ends with praise for God, just as it did at the beginning. The Psalm’s opening and concluding verses contain the phrase “Bless YHWH, my soul,” although they also contain other praise languages, particularly at the end. The entire Psalm praises God for creating and maintaining a stunning, elaborate, interdependent world full of God’s creations, including humans but primarily nonhuman animals for whom the earth was created. If humans are made in God’s image and designed “to rule or dominion” over creation in the same way that God does, then human “dominion or rule” must be involved in providing the same things to the creatures. God’s rule provides the three most crucial things for ensuring species’ survival: water, food, and habitat. Many species mentioned in the Psalm are not domesticated animals but rather wild creatures of creation. Humans give food and water to their flocks and herds.¹⁹

This passage discussed the wildlife of the whole planet. Humans must then allow the animal kingdom to enjoy its safe space in the incredible world God created for everyone. That is true “rule or dominion” over the created order. Humans have not

18 Elizabeth A. Johnson, *Ask the Beasts: Darwin and the God of Love* (London: Bloomsbury, 2015), 275.

19 Of course, humans intend to consume them.

“ruled”; Humans have “dominated.” Humans must change their behaviour. Humans must begin to act on many levels to save the planet. Clergy and church leaders must speak out on behalf of such actions to save the world for future generations. Psalm 104 indicates that God has placed humans in this world alongside other creatures, placing each human in its place.²⁰ Humans must occupy natural habitats without destroying the habitats of other animals. This would demonstrate valid “rule or dominion” over the plant and animal kingdoms.

Conclusion

Psalm 104 serves as a timeless reminder of the connection to nature and the sacred duty placed upon us as stewards of creation, especially considering the challenges of the Anthropocene. Thinking about the complex web of life that God has created forces us to consider the choices we make and the far-reaching effects of these choices. It is vital that we all work towards the protection of species, the preservation of habitats, and the reduction of human-induced harm. We can pave the way for a more peaceful sharing of the wonders of nature by adopting the wisdom of Psalm 104 and its celebration of the connection between humans and animals. By doing so, we respect the divine plan and ensure that the diversity and beauty of life on Earth will continue to overwhelm future generations. Let Psalm 104 serve as a strong call to action, encourage us to take on the role of real stewards of the environment, and protect the fragile balance that keeps us all alive.

²⁰ Richard Bauckham, *Living with Other Creatures: Green Exegesis and Theology* (Waco: Baylor University Press, 2011), 10.

2

THE NATURE AND CALLING OF THE CHURCH IN INDIA TODAY

Ben Jonathan Immanuel*

Introduction

Christians in India today have a storied history of being called into the faith and baptized by various missionary movements over a long period of time, ever since the 52 CE. But today time and space are very different. In an almost to-be fascist country with neoliberal polity, and an economy, coupled with one of the most famous social fragmentation systems in the world the Caste System, India remains popular owing to its technocratic, and glocal (global + local) impact in the world today. In an age of interconnected order, the church in India stands at a pivotal point with the very same call from Jesus Christ to become disciples.

In ever-changing political, social, economic, and religious landscapes, the Church of India has an ecumenical and evangelical legacy to take inspiration from but needs to carve out its own path to become a loving community in today's world. Part one of this article presents an analysis of the nature and calling of the Indian church in the present and a vision of what it might be going forward into the remainder of the 21st century. Part two appeals to present and future young church leaders in India, both in and out of seminaries (and those who still dream of seminaries), about the nature and calling of the church that we

* Ben Jonathan Immanuel is a ThM graduate from Princeton Theological Seminary, USA and, he holds BD from the United Theological College, Bangalore. He serves as Field Secretary with the India Sunday School Union, based in Coonor, India.

might envision together and partner with God in the mission of the Church.

An Analysis of Christianity in India during the First Quarter of the 21st century

According to a 2022 statistic¹, in India today, there are 348,000 congregations from at least 1,800 denominations, speaking 424 different languages. While in 1900, 50% Christians in India were Roman Catholics, followed by 31% Protestants, followed by smaller proportion of Orthodox and Independents, in 2020, Protestants were on top with 34%, followed by Catholics at 31%, Independents at 27%, and Orthodox at 8%. Pentecostals and Charismatics make up nearly 2% of the total population of the country. One among every 3 Christians in India today is Pentecostal or Charismatic. It is with this perspective that we must attempt to understand the nature and calling of the Church in India today. Any church in India today can broadly fit into either an evangelical or an ecumenical church, depending on their affinity and affiliation. While categorization is a biased tool, it helps provide a perspective to position ourselves and try to be the church in God's world today. Following the Roman Catholic church, "The second largest denomination today is the United Church of South India (CSI), which represents an ecumenical merger of Reformed, Congregational, Anglican, and Methodist denominations."²

While most of these churches could be called "ecumenical," given the actual grassroots reality, there "are many "charismatic" Christians within the traditional Protestant bodies as well."³ In addition to this, the Orthodox and other stand-alone traditions, we have a very diverse landscape of Christianity in India.

1 Gina A. Zurlo, *Global Christianity: A Guide to the World's Largest Religion from Afghanistan to Zimbabwe* (Michigan: Zondervan, 2022), 155-6.

2 Gina A. Zurlo, *Global Christianity...*,156

3 Gina A. Zurlo, *Global Christianity...*,156

Gladson Jathanna rightly opines that in India, “a democratic vision of *oikoumene* was often troubled, contested and sometimes even disappeared...a colonial and imperial mission of *oikoumene* was visibly evident throughout history.”⁴ Beginning with the 1910 Edinburgh conference, the colonial agenda of the ecumenical movement in India is illuminated with the purpose of evangelizing our land. However, the many complexities of the Indian vein continued to push Christianity to reimagine itself at every step. We must also acknowledge the categorical significance of the 1938 Tambaram and 1961 New Delhi global Christian conferences held in our country. Tambaram hosted the International Missionary Conference just before the second world war. This place has even been identified as where Christianity’s prominent shift to the global south in terms of numbers began taking shape.⁵ The conference in New Delhi proposed a model of “local ecumenism” saying that it is in local communities that the common life of Christ can be clearly tested.⁶ We must also remember the voices of M.M. Thomas and Augustine Ralla Ram, though operating in the ecumenical space, called out colonial behaviours and privileged the struggle for humanization.⁷ Today, we continue to have several voices speaking life into the context of Christianity in India, including young people across the country. We need more nuanced voices that can address the complex nature of the fabric of our nation, which is diverse in many aspects. It is with this in mind that we will look at the nexus that we should take up seriously going forward as a Church in India.

4 Gladson Jathanna, *Decolonizing Oikoumene* (New Delhi: ISPCK, 2020), 2.

5 I. Randall, “Tambaram, 1938: Christianity’s shift to the Global South”. *Transformation*, 40(4), 350-365. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02653788231206021>

6 Gladson Jathanna, *Decolonizing Oikoumene* (New Delhi: ISPCK, 2020), 24.

7 Gladson Jathanna, *Decolonizing Oikoumene* (New Delhi: ISPCK, 2020), 30-33.

Issues and Trends in Christianity in India to be prepared for the rest of the 21st century

The Indian Church, in different manifestations, thrives as a minority organization in a religiously diverse country. How the Church behaves will have adverse impacts across the nation because Christianity has always influenced Indian society. Aruna Gnanadason rightly maintains that the “issues of justice, human rights, ethnicity and minority issues, women and youth are all global in their dimensions and have their specific configurations in Asian societies.”⁸ We must begin by examining how this plays out in our milieu.

The Intersection between Caste, Gender, and Religion: The Identity-Community Conundrum

The Caste system in India continues to be the primary tool of fragmentation and hate within the country. Unfortunately, we still have caste-based churches and caste-specific worship services across India. Voices against the cruelty of this system have echoed throughout history, but it is too anchored into the social fabric of our lives that we must keep consciously engaging with it. One of the significant efforts by ecumenical bodies to address this issue was seen in 2010 at the National Ecumenical Conference on Justice for Dalits convened by the National Council of Churches in India in partnership with the World Council of Churches in New Delhi. The affirmation that came out of the conference,

Caste has fragmented us at all levels. Our tables are divided, our communities are divided, and our cemeteries are divided. Dalits bear the inflictions and injuries of such division. We are ashamed that as

⁸ Aruna Gnanadason, “The Contributions of the Ecumenical Movement in Asia to World Ecumenism” in Felix Wilfred ed., *The Oxford Handbook of Christianity in Asia* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2014), 142.

Christians we are unable to testify to the oneness of life as members of the body of Christ.⁹

An interlinked and unique category that the church in India will have to deal with is the identity-community conundrum. We are living in a time when traditional systems of family, gender, and marriage are broken down and reimagined. It is true that in organized councils and meetings, we continue to have calls for renewal in the churches to become “courageous and concrete witnesses to the body of Christ free of caste division, caste discrimination and caste violence.”¹⁰ It comes down to how we can translate this from the tables and chairs of conferences and comfortable spaces to the ground. As Rajkumar argues, “One of the ecumenical challenges for the Indian church is to be in solidarity with Dalit communities as they exercise their fundamental right to profess and follow a religion of their choice.”¹¹ To this end, I would also add tribal communities as well as mixed communities as well as every young person who is the future of the church in Indian society.

We fortunately have theological tools to engage meaningfully in this arena. As George Zachariah states, “Minjung, Dalit, Asian feminist, and Burakumin theologies reject the dominant triumphalist God concepts and reclaim God as the one who embodies their pain-pathos – and enables them in their search for self-hood and identity.”¹² More than ever, the Church must

9 “Affirmation of Faith on Justice for Dalits,” World Council of Churches, (Accessed December 9, 2023). <https://www.oikoumene.org/resources/documents/affirmation-of-faith-on-justice-for-dalits>

10 “Affirmation of Faith on Justice for Dalits,” World Council of Churches, (Accessed December 9, 2023). <https://www.oikoumene.org/resources/documents/affirmation-of-faith-on-justice-for-dalits>

11 Peniel Jesudasan Rufus Rajkumar, “No One Can Serve Christ and Caste: Indian Ecumenical Initiatives to Combat Caste” in Richard F. Young ed., *World Christianity and Interfaith Relations* (Augsburg Fortress Publishers, 2022), 225.

12 George Zachariah, “Re-imagining God of Life from the Margins” *The Ecumenical Review*, 65/ 1, March 2013: 47.

engage with issues concerning gender justice, food and livelihood justice, mental health, and wellbeing. We must never forget that India is notorious for being oppressive towards people of religious, ethnic, and gender minority. We therefore have an urgent call to resist all forms of heteropatriarchal, heterosexist, and capitalist systems, and while in the realm of liminality¹³ dream and work towards realizing a community of love.

Political and Economic climates

Uttering the word “Jesus Christ” in India today is not always a politically right thing to do. At least eight states in India currently have “anti-conversion” laws in place with penalties ranging from fines to imprisonment.¹⁴ While the majority of Christians come from Dalit or tribal backgrounds, they tend to lose government-sponsored affirmative action when they officially change their legal religion to Christianity.¹⁵ Therefore, we have the phenomenon of underground Christianity and the prevalence of invisible Christians who are very passionate about the faith, and who deeply understand the love of God in Jesus through the Holy Spirit. Our current Prime Minister has made ambitious plans to make the 21st century world look towards India as a global power. Through systematic plans since 2014, the ruling government has infiltrated the country with a larger-than-life image of what it means to be India. Unfortunately, while aiming for a 5 trillion USD economy¹⁶ on one hand, the

13 Liminality “is a transitional time in which persons are freed from social-structure hierarchy and role playing and, therefore, may be more open to what is new, experience a close communion with other persons, and become capable of prophetic critique of the existing social order.” Definition of Liminality is by Victor Turner quoted in Sang Hyun Lee, *From a Liminal Place: An Asian American Theology* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2010), x.

14 Gina A. Zurlo, *Global Christianity: A Guide to the World’s Largest Religion from Afghanistan to Zimbabwe* (Michigan: Zondervan, 2022), 156

15 Gina A. Zurlo, *Global Christianity...*, 156

16 <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/economy/indicators/india-to-become-usd-5-trillion-economy-third-largest-by-2027-rbi-dg-patra/articleshow/103844727.cms> (Accessed December 15, 2023)

government is allowing the gap between the rich and the poor to increase beyond control. There is a clear Hindutva agenda within this regime where Islamophobia and hatred towards all minority groups are on the rise. Among the minority groups that have not yet been visibly threatened are Christians in India, who continue to be invisibly persecuted in several ways. The prolonged ethnic clash in Manipur over the past year and, the inability of the political system to prevent bloodshed, and uphold peace are only a glimpse of what real life in India look like.¹⁷ India has just taken over from China as the most populous country in the world. Our global footprint is bigger than it has ever been, and therefore, the care is than it has ever been. The Church has to play great prophetic role to play in times such as this.

Emerging Church Traditions in India

A complexity of the history of Christianity in India continues to be its colonization mindset. We continue to borrow forms of worship and liturgy from the West and other alien traditions. While there have been several attempts at indigenization in the past and present, we continue to depend on the West for our liturgies, songs, worship styles and patterns, prayers, and theological language. This can be seen in the ever-growing number of new church movements and traditions in our country. The dependence on the West extends to the extent of glorifying theologies that are borrowed. However, the flipside to this is that these are the kinds of churches that are actually reaching the common Indian Christian in more appealing ways than most ecumenical churches do.

Although one could argue that there is disenchantment with the Church in the Western world, membership in any church in any southeast Asian context means much more than just church

¹⁷ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-67724692> (Accessed December 15, 2023)

life. Julius Bautista offers an interesting insight into this area. For minority groups, affiliation to churches enabled them to “facilitate connections with broader, transnational linkages with diasporic ethnic networks, thus helping them reach beyond their immediate vicinities and tap into wider community identities.”¹⁸ This is a trend worth exploring. Our churches must be more connected to the actual lives of our people to remain relevant. It is in this context that we realise that the future of ecumenism in India, at least in the genuine attempts to work together, cannot be linked to any specific agency or church-related body. The solution lies “in such basic concerns as sharing Scripture in local languages and then turning to care for the least well-off and most oppressed in each context.”¹⁹ To facilitate cross-denominational connections and relations, we must begin first with empathy, and develop friendship, and then hope to organically work together given the current situations.

Technology and the Earth

The Church is no longer as it was before Covid-19. There has been a boom in digital communication. Most church gatherings occur virtually. We know that televangelism and charismatic Christian figures continue to influence national Christianity with the aid of high-quality technology. Perhaps, this is an avenue that needs to be considered as well addressed. However, the dangers of such a revolution must also be held in tension. Rajkumar observes, “In permeating through technology, humans have not only found a new master to control over, but have subtly moved the authority to technology to enslave humans.”²⁰ We should think

18 Julius Bautista, “Christianity in Southeast Asia: Colonialism, Nationalism and the Caveats to Conversion” in Felix Wilfred ed., *The Oxford Handbook of Christianity in Asia* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2014), 226.

19 Scott W. Sunquist, “Asia” in Geoffrey Wainwright and Paul McPartlan eds., *The Oxford Handbook of Ecumenical Studies* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2021), 526

20 R. Christopher Rajkumar, “Humanising ‘4th Industrial Revolution:’ A Mission Agenda”, *NCC Review*, Vol. CXXXVIII No. 04, May 2018: 47.

responsibly and wisely in handling Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Internet Age.

As a final point of consideration, I draw your attention to the ongoing environmental crisis. We have activists all around the world conscientious about this fact even as we continue to experience disruptive and unusual weather patterns, growing numbers of natural disasters, and calamities. Coming out of a pandemic has taught us how changing in one place affects change everywhere. We are living in times of war especially between Russia-Ukraine, and Israel-Palestine. Our Church is called for and in and to such a time as this.

An Appeal to the Church

We as the Church have a call²¹ *at hand*. You and I are uniquely different. We are so because we serve a uniquely different God. As present and future leaders of the complex church in India, this is an appeal for partnership in the work of the kingdom²² of our God.

We believe in One Triune God, Father/Mother/Parent, the only begotten Son, Jesus Christ, and the Holy Spirit. In God's life, we see community and have been made in God's image; we are called to be beings in communion. We are called to hold oneness and manyness in creative tension. God's lifesaving Word and Spirit must be a trinitarian formula through which

21 Dirk Smit, the one who formulated the Belhar Confession that addressed apartheid in South Africa, says, "the calling comes as one (the *generalis vocatio*), because it is the human being, the person, who is called by God...the immediate, spiritual calling (the *immediata vocatio*) to believe and to be baptised, and the mediatory, earthly calling (the *mediata vocatio*), to serve God and your neighbour in your class and work. Dirk Smit, "Church and work? Questions concerning the Christian view of "calling" in Ernst M. Conradie (ed.) *Essays in Public Theology: Collected Essays 1* (Stellenbosch: University of the West Cape, 2007), 458.

22 "Kingdom of God" is the language Jesus used. Although we can reimagine what this means for us today, we still need to be longing for the vision of a kingdom that Jesus had for us.

we can pattern our lives as Christians in the here and now. We are called as the disciples of Jesus Christ to perform the work of reconciliation and recreation.

We believe in the Bible, which reveals to us the greatest incomprehensible wisdom: that God is love. All our canons, whether Roman Catholic, Protestant, Orthodox, or any other Christian tradition, have been given to us through divine providence and human discernment for our edification. We are called to, in prayer, faithfully meditate on the Scriptures Day and night. Perhaps, we can strive to do this together in community even as we consciously and meaningfully, with integrity, engage the many religious texts and traditions in our land.

We believe in the Church²³ in and for our Time and Space.

While some would prefer the word ‘ecclesia’, ‘church’ is the real-world term. It is what common people know and are familiar with. Church is a building. Church is a gathering of people. Church is an activity. Church is a feeling, an emotion, one that is very different with the current change in living conditions. Church is a “called out” community. Church is a community with expectations. Church is a change-making and influential social movement. Church is a prophetic community. Church is a dedicated time and space, physical or virtual, for communion with God and God’s creation. From this understanding, Church life can be defined as communion with God, communion with oneself, and communion with the neighbour, which is all of creation.²⁴

²³ Church from the Greek word *ekklesia* is further elaborated through the “marks of the church” found in several places in our readings in the course. I picked six of them in my appeal that are crucial for our understanding of Church.

²⁴ Ben Jonathan Immanuel, “The Nexus between COVID-19 and the Fourth Industrial Revolution: Challenges and Opportunities in Church Life,” *NCC Review* (September 2020): 32.

We are gifted with Kerygma²⁵, the proclamation of the gospel (good news). What is good news for a Christian in India today other than the abundant life (John 10:10) that God provides? Good news for a poor person is food, clothing, and shelter. Good news for the prisoner and bonded labourer is freedom and joy. Good news for the blind and sick person is medical care. Good news for the orphans and the oppressed is home and family. Good news for the unemployed is that they have a stable job to care for their household.

We are invited to Koinonia²⁶ for fellowship in the Spirit. We all grew up with an understanding of “all Indians are my brothers and sisters.” Whether we like it or not, this is our call to cause kindred spirit among our neighbours. Furthermore, who is our neighbour?²⁷ Should this be a question at all? One that is not us, a person from another group, is our neighbour. Therefore, we must rid ourselves of the “member church syndrome.” Each of us is Christ’s disciples and each of us is the Church. We must also never forget the least among us, those fringe congregations that are faithful to becoming disciples of Jesus.

We are called to be faithful to Didache²⁸, teaching and instruction. We are called to be mindful of theologies of the God, the Church, and the Sacraments. When we operate out of love and not fear, we will always speak truth to power, and in doing

25 An imagination of Luke 4:18,19

26 Dietrich Bonhoeffer says, “We can only achieve perfect liberty and enjoy fellowship with Jesus when his command, his call to absolute discipleship, is appreciated in its entirety. Only the man (sic.) who follows the command of Jesus single-mindedly, and unresistingly lets his (sic.) yoke rest upon him, finds his burden easy, and under its gentle pressure receives the power to persevere in the right way. The command of Jesus is hard, unutterably hard, for those who try to resist it. But for those who willingly submit, the yoke is easy, and the burden is light.” Dietrich Bonhoeffer, *The Cost of Discipleship* (New York: Touchstone Edition, 1995), 37.

27 The imagination of Luke 17:11-19 where Jesus uses the Greek word *Allogenes* meaning “of another tribe.” This is the only mention of the word in the NT.

28 An imagination of and further steps for the BEM/Lima document (1982).

so, we will enable our faith communities to be more like Jesus Christ, forgiving, pardoning, and loving. We need to open our tables and be more appreciative of all our unique traditions. We need to learn from each other and share in each other's joy and sadness in our ministerial journeys.

We are expected to creatively engage the rhythms of worship in *Leitourgia*²⁹. Let us make conscious efforts to keep our liturgies creative, accessible, and inclusive. Our liturgies, hymns, and songs are not personal property to have claim over but are shared resources, our theological commons. They have the power to reimagine God's dreams for our world. May this be our prophetic space for engaging our contexts.

We are blessed and challenged to participate in *Diakonia*³⁰, service within the church and beyond. We assume responsibility for hospitality, congregational care, and care for our neighbourhood and all creation. We must strive to conscientize ourselves and our communities to be stewards of God's creation and not exploiters. Some of us will be ordained, others may not. But we must remain faithful to the call and acknowledge the call each one of us carries that is given by God to love God's people.

We aim for *Marturia*³¹, a witness within and beyond. The call to discipleship is a call to be, and die. While Jesus affirms us that the burden will be light, he also demonstrates us by example that we must be in the world and for the world and not the world. This does not mean that we will withdraw from the world. On the contrary, we are required to engage intentionally with all the systems of our country whether political, religious, social, economic, or legal.

29 An Imagination of Ephesians 5:15-21

30 An imagination of the several ways disciples worked together as in the book of Acts.

31 An imagination of 2 Timothy 2.

This is no boring feat;
This is exciting prospect;
This is the call to us, as the Church, to love, to dream, to be;
Together, we can do more than we could ever do alone.

JOHN WESLEY THEOLOGY OF COVENANT: A FOUNDATION FOR SERVANT LIVING

F. Lal Chhandama*

John Wesley's Covenant Prayer¹

I am no longer my own, but yours.
 Put me to what you will, rank me with whom you will;
 put me to doing, put me to suffering;
 let me be employed for you, or laid aside for you,
 exalted for you, or brought low for you;
 let me be full, let me be empty,
 let me have all things, let me have nothing:
 I freely and wholeheartedly yield all things to your
 pleasure and disposal.
 And now, glorious and blessed God,
 Father, Son and Holy Spirit,
 you are mine and I am yours. So be it.
 And the covenant now made on earth, let it be ratified in
 heaven. Amen.

An Overview of The Wesleyan Theology of the Covenant: Historical development

Medieval Theology marked a pivotal phase in the development of covenant theology, setting the stage for later Reformation initiated by thinkers like Martin Luther and John Calvin. This

* F. Lal Chhandama has completed his Master of Theology from the United Theological college, Bangalore. He is a church worker in the Salvation Army church, Aizawl, Mizoram.

1 A.B Lawson, *John Wesley and the Christian Ministry* (London: SPCK, 1963), 28.

era witnessed a transformative shift in the understanding of covenant, notable the emergence of the “covenant of grace.”² It was characterized by the influence of scholasticism, a theological method aimed at synthesizing Christian doctrine and the philosophical insights of ancient scholars, notably Aristotle.

Prominent scholastic theologians, including Thomas Aquinas, played influential roles during this epoch.³ Covenant theology in the Middle Ages was also influenced by Augustinian thought, particularly Augustine’s writings on the interplay between divine grace and human volition. It was during this period that the concept of the “covenant of grace” gained prominence, with theologians like Bernard of Clairvaux and Anselm of Canterbury exploring the notion that God’s relationship with humanity rested on His benevolence and unearned favour, rather than human worthiness.⁴

Key Theological Concepts

John Wesley’s sermon, “The Righteousness of Faith,” (1746) gives the fullest description of his covenant theology. His prayer says:⁵

“The Apostle does not here oppose the covenant given by Moses, to the covenant given by Christ. If we ever imagined this, it was for want of observing, that the latter as well as the former part of these words were spoken by Moses himself to the people of Israel, and that concerning the covenant which then was. (Deuteronomy 30:11, 12, 14.) But it is the covenant of grace, which God, through Christ, hath established with men in all ages,

2 David Bagchi and David C. Steinmetz, eds., *The Cambridge Companion to Reformation Theology* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004), 117.

3 Gills Emery O.P and Matthew Levering, eds., *Aristotle in Aquinas’s Theology* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015), 97.

4 J.N.D. Kelly, *Early Christian Doctrines* (London: Adam & Charles Black, 1968), 415.

5 John Wesley, *The Works of John Wesley Volume 5: The Life of John Wesley First Series of Sermon (1-39)* (Ages Software, Albany: Version 1.0, 1997),

(as well before and under the Jewish dispensation, as since God was manifest in the flesh,) which St. Paul here opposes to the covenant of works, made with Adam while in Paradise, but commonly supposed to be the only covenant which God had made with man, particularly by those Jews of whom the Apostle writes.”

In his sermon, the Jewish dispensation is clearly linked to the covenant of grace. Wesley taught that the covenant of works was established with supralapsarian⁶ Adam as the federal head of the human race, which required perfect obedience from him, and his posterity was fulfilled and abolished through the work of Christ. In Wesley’s thought, attaining justification under the terms of this covenant is forcefully underscored. Wesley appealed to the doctrine of the covenant of works to emphasize the impossibility of good works as a means of entering life. Although established by God through the infralapsarian⁷ Adam,

-
- 6 Supralapsarianism is a theological stance within the broader scope of Reformed theology and is, notably linked to theologians such as Theodore Beza and Francis Turretin. Its distinctive feature lies in its perspective on God’s decrees, particularly in the context of predestination and humanity’s fall from grace. In the context of “supralapsarian Adam,” it signifies the belief that as part of His eternal design, God predetermined specific individuals to either attain salvation or endure damnation before the world’s creation. This predetermination extends to the understanding that Adam, the biblical figure originating from the Book of Genesis and the first human created by God, along with all of humanity, would inevitably fall into sin as a result of God’s ordained decree of the fall. See Kenneth J. Collins, *The Theology of John Wesley* (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 2007), 65.
- 7 Infralapsarianism, a theological perspective within the broader domain of Reformed theology, presents a specific understanding of God’s decrees, particularly in relation to predestination and humanity’s fall from grace. In this framework, the sequence of God’s decrees is distinct: it first entails the decree of the fall, marking the determination that humanity would descend into sin; and subsequently, it involves the decree of predestination, which designates certain individuals for salvation while others are destined for reprobation. In the context of “infralapsarian Adam,” this concept signifies the belief that, within, God’s eternal plan, He selected or predestined specific individuals for salvation or condemnation, with these choices made after considering humanity’s descent into sin through Adam’s act of disobedience. In essence, the decree of predestination is seen as following to God’s decree concerning the fall. See Kenneth J. Collins, *The Theology of John Wesley* (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 2007), 73.

the covenant of grace was fulfilled through the atoning work of Christ and requires faith; God “imputes his [the believer’s] faith to him for righteousness.” The righteousness of the law may be summarized by the words ‘Do this and live’; whereas the righteousness of faith may best be summarized by the words ‘Believe and live.’ Supralapsarian Adam was the only human being who was under the covenant of works; all other human beings are under the covenant of grace.

John Wesley wholeheartedly accepted the concept of Covenant of grace as a pivotal theological concept. This covenant, also known as the New Covenant, represents a divine pact by which God extends salvation and grace to humanity solely through faith in Jesus Christ. Within this framework, Wesley perceived the Covenant of Grace as a channel through which God’s unearned favour and forgiveness are generously bestowed upon sinners, firmly rooted in God’s boundless love and longing for the restoration of a deep relationship with humanity. In this covenant, Christ serves as the intermediary, facilitating believers’ entry into a personal and transformative relationship with God through their faith in Him. This faith subsequently leads to justification and sanctification, culminating in a life of holiness and spiritual transformation. Wesley ardently believed in the universal accessibility of this covenant relationship, asserting that God’s grace is prevenient in nature and, signifying that it goes before us, beckoning us towards God even before we are conscious of it. This concept of prevenient grace is intimately intertwined with the Covenant of Grace.⁸

While Wesley used covenantal language in his preface, he endeavoured to avoid the errors of the Calvinistic doctrine of the covenants. Wesley countered Hervey’s argument that the covenant of grace had changed the locus of obedience from man to Christ by asserting that this was an unscriptural way of speaking. When Hervey argues that the covenant of grace was

8 Albert C. Outler, ed., *John Wesley* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1964), 124-125.

not made with Adam and his posterity but with Christ, Wesley argues that the words were not spoken to Christ but to him and give no intimation of any covenant. Further, Wesley maintains that Christ did not fulfil the conditions of the covenant of grace; human beings by grace can fulfil the conditions of the covenant, which are, in part, repentance and faith. 'What Christ has done is the foundation, not the condition of our justification. Wesley described the new covenant made possible by Christ's sacrificial death and human participation in the covenant through faith.' To assert otherwise is to fall into the trap of antinomianism.⁹ Wesley's evident concern with the Calvinist doctrine of the covenant is the inherent theoretical antinomianism.

Prevenient Grace

John Wesley developed prevenient grace to have a covenant; he was not comfortable with Article 17 (Anglican Thirty-nine Articles), which discusses Predestination and Elections.

While he struggled to accept this concept at the time of his ordination, he developed an understanding of prevenient grace into one of his major theological precepts. Wesley preached that God's grace was universally given to everyone equally. He meant that the Grace of God is not given to few but is given to others. Wesley states:¹⁰

"... it [grace] is free in all to whom it is given. It does not depend on any power or merit in man; no, not in any degree, neither in whole, nor in part. It does not in any wise depend either on the good works or righteousness of the receiver; not on anything he had done, or anything he is grace free in all. No way depending on any power or merit in man, but on God alone, who freely gave his own Son, and 'with him freely giveth us all thing."

9 J. Russell Frazier, "John Wesley's Covenantal and Dispensational view of Salvation History," *Wesley and Methodist Studies* 1(2009): 33-54.

10 Albert Outler, *Wesley, Works* Vol 3, Sermon "Free Grace," 544.

Prevenient grace, foundational in Wesleyan theology, precedes human response by, awakening individuals to their spiritual needs and enabling them to choose salvation. It forms the foundation of the covenant between God and humanity, and empowers individuals to initiate relationship with God. In Wesley's view, the covenant signifies a commitment to loving God and others, pursuing holiness, and growing in grace. Responding to prevenient grace with faith and obedience, individuals enter into a covenantal relationship with God. Within this relationship, sustaining grace continually empowers believers to progress in holiness and maintain their faith journey.¹¹ The covenant is not a one-time event but an ongoing process of growth and transformation sustained, by God's grace. Through prevenient and sustaining grace, individuals exercise their free will to engage in a meaningful relationship with God, characterized by faithfulness and growth.

Servant Living in Community

John Wesley's concept of "Servant Living in Community" emphasized the importance of having a servant's heart, actively engaging in works of mercy, promoting social holiness, participating in small group accountability, and living out one's faith through practical acts of service and love. The following briefly explains of the themes mentioned in this paper.

Servant Heart¹²

Wesley believed that a genuine Christian should embody a servant's heart. This entailed possessing qualities of modesty, altruism, and readiness to assist others. He urged individuals to mirror Jesus' example, who came not to be served but to provide service to humanity. Wesley placed significant emphasis on the

11 J. Brazier Green, *John Wesley and William Law* (London: The Epworth Press, 1945), 83

12 Neil Dixon, *Called to Love and Praise* (Peterborough: Methodist Publishing House, 1990), 13-14.

value of humility as a foundation for a servant's disposition. He encouraged people to nurture a mindset of humility, acknowledging their limitations, imperfections, and reliance on God. Recognizing one's need for divine grace and guidance was deemed crucial in faithfully practicing the Christian faith. Embracing a servant's heart encompassed a dedication to selflessness in Wesley's teachings. He motivated believers to prioritize the welfare and concerns of others over their personal desires and interests. This selfless attitude was firmly rooted in the biblical principle of "love your neighbour as yourself." At the core of Wesley's concept of a servant's heart was a sincere enthusiasm for helping others. He firmly believed that Christians should actively seek opportunities to lend a helping hand, provide support, and uplift those in need. This willingness to serve extended to acts of kindness, charity, and expressions of mercy.

Works of Mercy¹³

John Wesley's emphasis on "works of mercy" stems from his belief in practical Christianity, inspired by Jesus' compassionate examples in the New Testament. These actions, ranging from providing basic necessities to caring for the vulnerable, reflect Christ's love for humanity. Wesley urged Christians to engage in these acts as expressions of their faith, emphasizing the interconnectedness of physical and spiritual well-being. While addressing immediate needs, Wesley also emphasized the importance of offering spiritual support and guidance. For him, works of mercy were not about earning salvation but about responding to God's grace with gratitude. They embodied the love and mercy received by believers from God and extended it to others. Wesley's teachings portrayed the holistic nature of

¹³ Outler, ed., *John Wesley*, 235-36. E. Douglas Bebb, *Wesley: A Man with a Concern* (London: The Epworth Press, 1950), 30-31.

Christian service, integrating both physical and spiritual care into one's Christian journey.

Social Holiness¹⁴

John Wesley's concept of "social holiness" goes beyond individual pursuit and focuses on communal expression. He believed that personal holiness was intrinsically linked to the life of a Christian community. Social holiness should naturally lead to active social engagement and transformation. This view challenged the notion of holiness as limited to personal piety or individual morals; instead, it extended holiness to the public sphere and examined how individuals interacted with the world and wider communities. Wesley encouraged congregants to collaborate to address social issues and advocate for justice. Social holiness meant collective efforts within Methodist communities to bring about positive change, including caring for the marginalized, and promoting social reforms, thereby bridging the gap between personal faith and, societal engagement for a more just and compassionate society.

Covenantal aspects of servant living¹⁵

In Covenant Theology, John Wesley highlighted the concept of God establishing a covenantal relationship with humanity, marked by God's grace and humanity's response in faith and obedience. Likewise, in the practice of servant living, individuals who aim to express their faith through practical actions are essentially acknowledging and responding to God's covenant of love and grace by serving others. This covenantal connection with God serves as both motivation and empowerment for engaging in acts of service and, demonstrating love to their fellow neighbours. Within Covenant Theology, an emphasis is

14 Lawson, *John Wesley, and the Christian Ministry*, 73-74.

15 Joseph Basappa Suray, *Towards a Theology of Universality: John Wesley's Socio-Economic, Political & Moral Insights on British Class & Indian Caste Distinctions* (New Delhi: Christian World Imprints, 2015), 403-04.

placed on the pursuit of holiness, because, those in covenant with God are called to lead lives characterized by sanctity. In the context of servant living, holiness extends beyond individual aspirations; it becomes a communal and pragmatic endeavour. John Wesley believed that authentic holiness manifests in one's active serving and caring for others. Therefore, living as a servant within the community becomes a tangible expression of holiness and a means of honouring the covenantal commitment to God. In addition, Wesleyan theology places significant importance on the Christian community as an environment conducive to spiritual growth and the cultivation of holiness. Methodist societies and class meetings were viewed as covenantal communities where members mutually held each other accountable in their Christian journeys. Servant living is practiced within the framework of this covenantal community, where individuals provide support and encouragement to one another through their acts of service and expressions of mercy. Consequently, the community itself transforms into a covenantal space where members collectively endeavour to live out their faith through selfless servitude.

Community as a context for servant living¹⁶

In John Wesley's theology, community is vital to the practice of servanthood. He emphasised that the Christian journey should be communal rather than solitary. Methodist societies urge members to break spiritual isolation and promote transparency in their spiritual experiences. Mutual accountability within these groups helped human development and promoted servanthood. Individuals were inspired by their open dedication to service, but their activities were also scrutinised by the community. Wesley envisioned a Christian society where members could find inspiration and encouragement for service. When individuals felt compelled to perform acts of charity or social activism, the

16 Neil Dixon, *Called to Love and Praise* (Peterborough: Methodist Publishing House, 1990), 40-43.

community rallied in support, offering physical and spiritual assistance. Wesley witnessed that servant living's influence increased the community's working for greater societal issues. This collaborative method, founded on Wesleyan theology, reflected the shared character of the early Christian church. Wesley believed that the Christian societies facilitate both exterior service and interior regeneration. Acts of service within this community fostered faith and served as opportunities for spiritual growth and sanctification, expressing holiness as the early Christians described in the Book of Acts.

Conclusion

John Wesley's theology integrates Covenant Theology with Servant Living in a unified framework. Covenant Theology, which is based on God's grace and human reaction, informs Wesley's understanding of God's relationship with humanity. Servant Living expands on this principle by, encouraging believers to respond to God's grace by serving others. Preventive grace enables one to live with a motif of service, allowing people to recognise their need for God and form covenantal connections. This commitment forms the foundation of Servant Living, in which faith and obedience stem from preventive grace. Wesley focuses on the practical aspects of Christianity, emphasising the significance of helping others and embodying community holiness. This synergy between Covenant Theology and Servant Living emphasises the community pursuit of spiritual growth and social holiness. Wesley's theology promotes a comprehensive Christian life by instilling faith, love, and service in Wesleyan communities around the world following Christ's example. One can affirm that it can be a paradigm for Christian living, even in the context of plurality of faiths, to promote a committed Christian faith and witness.

DIVINE EMPATHY AND HUMAN APATHY: THE CASE OF JONAH

P D Sengvaidam Chiru*

Introduction

Apathy is a lack of interest, enthusiasm, or concern/ behaviour that shows no interest or unwillingness to take action. The Old Testament teaches us that God created human beings in God's image and likeness. God created human families in and through Adam and Eve. One can notice divine empathy when humans fall and become disobedient to God. God has not left them to their fates of sinful nature but received them, forgave them, and redirected their lives as part of God's initial promises and purposes (Genesis 1:26-28). In such a context, one can understand God's eternal plan and his (sic) empathetic view of humankind through the elucidation of biblical theology. However, human apathy has become a negation of divine empathy, which eventually projected the human kind as insensitive and unconscious in the divine plan of salvation for the entire human world.

When we read the prophetic narratives, the book of Jonah stands as a peculiar prophetic text that initially negated the divine plan for salvation for the people of the Ninevites, the non-Israelites. Prophet Jonah expresses his discomfort with the way God planned to save the people of the Ninevites. God teaches Jonah the divine mystery and divine providence to save every human community because it is part of a divine empathetic

* P D Sengvaidam Chiru has completed his M.Th in the Old Testament at the United Theological College, Bangalore.

gesture during fallen human life. This essay elucidates profound divine empathy against human apathy, a nemesis that disturbs amicable human relations for nothing. This essay affirms that divine empathy can be a remedy for human apathy, and can renavigate human life according to God's plan for human salvation.

A Bird's Eye View of the Book of Jonah

The Book of Jonah dates from the 8th century, probably around 760 BCE. Unlike the other minor prophets, this book is a story of the prophet's personal struggle with God over his mission to Nineveh. Nineveh was a large city that was well fortified, and it was the capital city for the Assyrians, the enemies of Israel at that time. On the other hand, Jonah is patriotic to his nation, Israel. No wonder the divine command to go to Nineveh, the capital of the empire that for decades had terrorized the people of Israel, came as a jolting shock to Jonah. The Bible indicates that Jonah immediately reacted to the divine commission. "Jonah ran away from the Lord and headed for Tarshish" (Jonah 1:3). The prophet had to act as God's messenger when his message was good for his people. But Jonah is unwilling to send a message to an enemy who might harm his country. The book shows that God was interested not only for his own people but also for people who, are outside the covenantal relationship.

Probably, God wants the people of Israel to be light to the world so that the world can learn the salvific acts of God. However, the book shows that Jonah has been upset because God is gracious and merciful to the people of Nineveh. Jonah's uncertain behaviour represents human apathetic behaviour that presents a tendency to reject God's mission for the whole world.

Divine Empathy corrects Jonah's Apathy:

Both Jonah 1:1 and 2 kings 14:25 identify Jonah as the son of Amittai, and the book of kings gives further information

that he was from Gath-hepher, a town in lower Galilee about three miles northeast of Nazareth, in the ancient tribal claim of Zebulun. Jonah had a mind of his own. Even when he knew that he had lost the war, he still waged his personal battle (4:1-11). Brevard S. Child understands that it was a very human reaction that Jonah should be thankful for being delivered, but he is resentful about God's plan for Nineveh.¹ Jonah was an ardent nationalist, pro-Israel and anti-foreign; he was a poet and was also capable of being peevish and stubborn, even against God."² He does not want to conduct a divine mission to a non-Israeli nation. Nineveh was Assyria's capital, and it killed and captured the Israelites. Nineveh became a scary place for the Israelites, and they were often at war with them. Therefore, Jonah may be scared of getting hurt if he visits the enemies of Israel. Jonah learns that Nineveh is an idolatrous, proud, and ruthless nation that, focuses on invading and winning the world. Jonah wants Nineveh destroyed. He feels that they deserve God's judgement.

At the same time, Jonah fails to learn that God's empathy extends to the human world, including the people of Nineveh. Jonah does not want to see God's mercy extended to his enemies; he suspects that God, being merciful and compassionate (4:2), will not perform his punishment on Nineveh. He does not want to be God's instrument of mercy for that hated, non-Israeli nation. He assumed that if he had warned Nineveh's people, about the dangers of asking God for forgiveness. Furthermore, if they asked God to forgive them, Jonah knew that God would forgive them because he (sic) was loving and full of mercy. Jonah wants his God to be merciful and compassionate only to his people. He cannot tolerate God being merciful to other nations (4:1). He does not believe that any people other than Israel are worth God's merciful will. He would be happy if God punished and

1 Brevard S. Child, *Introduction to the Old Testament as Scripture* (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1979), 423-24.

2 D. Stuart, *Hosea-Jonah* (Waco: Word Books, 1987), 431.

destroyed the nation, he hated the most.³ God wants Jonah to show concern for and love for the Nineveh city even though they are not part of God's covenantal community. At the same time, Jonah wants to see this foreign nation punished, thinking that they are not related to him or his people. Literally, he was not interested in saying any words to the city. At this juncture, God rebukes and questions Jonah's strategic move with a mission of God in the world. God's empathy corrects Jonah and, sets him on the right path to fulfil the mission of God in the world.

Human Apathy: Nemesis in a healthy Society

The successful result of Jonah's preaching dismays and angers the prophet (4:1) instead of satisfying him. He is upset and infuriated by God's decree. When he preached the doom of Nineveh, the oppressor of his country, he wanted to see its punishment executed and hoped to exult in the destruction of the enemy. As a sign of patriotic service to his people, Jonah belonged to be an instrument in this destruction. Ironically, God's mercy shattered all his ambitions. The prophet is angry in the place of exceeding exultation. Here he gives the reason for fleeing from the Lord (1:3). He knew that God was gracious and compassionate (4:2), and this nature would not have allowed Nineveh's destruction.⁴ Jonah's hope has now turned into despair, and instead of rendering his active share in punishing the enemy nation, he has helped the enemy escape from destruction. The prophet is deeply frustrated with his sad fate.

Even when Jonah objects to God's mercy towards Nineveh, God continues to be compassionate to Jonah by providing him shade in the scorching heat of the day, and Jonah enjoys this gracious gesture of God (4:6). Then God uses the plant to teach

3 Sebastian Kizhakkeyil, *The Twelve Minor Prophets. An Exegetical Commentary* (Bangalore: Asian Trading Corporation, 2006), 253-254.

4 Sebastian Kizhakkeyil, *The Twelve Minor Prophets. An Exegetical Commentary*, 260-261.

Jonah that he is wrong in his attitude. The plant withers (4:7); the day becomes a unbearably hot day (4:8). Then God resumes the dialogue with Jonah asking him why he feels pity on the plant (4:9-10) and shows him that God has more reason to be compassionate to Nineveh than Jonah has to feel pity towards the plant (4:11).⁵ It is true that God cares for every soul. God doesn't want anyone else to suffer from anything. Even if a person suffers, God wants one of us to help them. God is angry with Jonah for his apathy towards Nineveh, and he (sic) shows Jonah a life lesson he (sic) loves and is concerned about every nation.

Jonah's apathy towards Nineveh is a nemesis for the Ninevites, and their gesture against anyone against anyone can be counted as a nemesis for society. Perhaps the Ninevites are unaware of the living God, but this does not mean that they deserve severe punishment from God. One should help them to know and realize the God of mercy and kindness. Instead of preaching to Nineveh's people, Jonah chooses to escape and undermines God's mission. This behaviour of Jonah appears to be his nemesis that struck him down during his prophetic vocation. Jonah's nemesis is a prime example neglecting God's mission to the world, thereby causing the world suffer from lacking the agents of God to build better lives.

Implication for the Contemporary Society and Churches

It is God's plan for humankind to inculcate compassion for one another. Humankind needs to stand for one another, help each other in times of need, and be kind to each other. God has created humankind in God's own image and likeness so that humankind can love one another and be kind to each other. Certainly, living nature separates humankind from all other creatures. The image and likeness of God that we carry allow us to have fellowship

⁵ Sebastian Kizhakkeyil, *The Twelve Minor Prophets. An Exegetical Commentary*, 261.

with God, and to hold rightful relationships with one another. The apathy of humankind certainly makes God angry with the human world.

God is not happy with the decision made by Jonah when he tried to run away from Nineveh. Jonah is out of concern for Nineveh, and he wants Nineveh's people to be punished. One can argue that Jonah does not have any right to decide that Nineveh's people should be punished for their wicked deeds. Instead, Jonah's prime mission would be to deliver the message of repentance and salvation to people in need. God wants Jonah to preach the message of salvation to Nineveh's people. Even though the people of Nineveh were considered the most wicked, sinful, and dangerous, Jonah's mission is to help them repent and become transformed considering the message of God. However, Jonah's apathy towards the people of Nineveh angers God, and it eventually leads Jonah to experience God's profound concern that leads him to change his attitude towards the people of Nineveh.

Conclusion

Divine empathy is beyond human comprehension, and humankind is called to learn of it, and put it into practice as and when it is demanded in any situation. The book of Jonah and the attitude of Jonah inform a prophet whose mission is supposed to take the message of repentance and salvation to that, he has not cared for the empathy of God for the world. Jonah, as a prophet, neglected God's mission for the people of Ninevites. However, God corrects him, teaching him the worth of recognizing God's profound concern for people of the world, the people of Ninevites, in this context. Jonah's apathetic attitude does not allow him to function as an instrument of God for the mission of God. Jonah's apathy has become a nemesis for his prophetic vocation.

Apathy is one of the greatest enemies in society. “People suffer not because of wicked people, but because of the silence of good and educated people.” Like Jonah, when people go astray or when unsociable activities take place, society or churches may think that it is not our concern, and why should we interfere in the matters of others. Jonah’s personal experience with the empathetic move of God enables us to realize that God’s mission shouldn’t be categorized based on humankind’s apathetic attitudes. God’s empathy leads Jonah to learn and realize the danger of apathy, and it eventually places him as a true agent of God in the act of transforming the people of Nineveh. In the context of exclusivism and hatred, individuals and communities must sow seeds of peace and amicability. Instead of responding with an apathetic attitude to an antagonistic situation, the people of God are called to learn and hold on to being divinely empathetic in response to conflict situations. Furthermore, it is the responsibility of individuals and communities to preach the message of salvation, peace, and reconciliation to societies that suffer from fanaticism and violence.

5

MINDFUL FAITH: INTEGRATING MINDFULNESS INTO CHRISTIAN COUNSELLING

Akhil A O*

In today's world, mental health concerns are becoming more prevalent, and counsellors are continually seeking effective methods to ensure their clients' well-being. Among these methods, mindfulness has gained significant attention because it can reduce stress, enhance emotional regulation, and promote overall mental health¹. However, the concept of mindfulness, which is often rooted in Eastern spiritual traditions, may initially seem at odds with the principles of Christian counselling. This article explores the potential for integrating mindfulness into Christian counselling, arguing that mindful practices can complement and enrich client's spiritual lives without compromising their faith.

Fundamentally, mindfulness is the practice of maintaining a non-judgemental awareness of this moment. This practice aligns with several Christian teachings, such as the call to "love the Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind" (Matthew 22:37), emphasizing the importance of mindful awareness in understanding and experiencing God's love. In a world where atheistic perspectives often challenge

* Rev. Akhil A O is a presbyter in the Church of South India, South Kerala Diocese.

1 Jon Kabat-Zinn, *Wherever You Go, There You Are: Mindfulness Meditation in Everyday Life* (New York: Hyperion, 1994), 42-44.

spiritual beliefs, mindful awareness can help believers make a significant difference in their personal and communal lives.

The Theological Basis for Mindfulness in Christianity: Scriptural Foundations

The concept of mindfulness, defined as present-focused, non-judgemental awareness, resonates with various Biblical teachings. For instance, the practice of being fully present and aware can be linked to Jesus' teachings on worry and anxiety. In Matthew 6:34, Jesus advises, "Therefore do not worry about tomorrow, for tomorrow will worry about itself. Each day has enough trouble of its own". This verse emphasizes the importance of focusing on this moment, a core tenet of mindfulness. Furthermore, the Psalms often reflect a mindfulness-like focus on the present and a deep, contemplative engagement with God's presence. Psalm 46:10, "Be still, and know that I am God," encourages believers to pause, reflect, and connect deeply with God in the present moment. This stillness and reflective state can be seen as a form of mindfulness that fosters spiritual awareness and peace. The New Testament also offers insights into mindfulness. For example, the Apostle Paul writes in Philippians 4:6-7, "Do not be anxious about anything, but in every situation, by prayer and petition, with thanksgiving, present your requests to God. God's peace, which transcends all understanding, will guard your hearts and minds in Christ Jesus". Here, Paul advises a mindful approach to dealing with anxiety that focuses on prayer, thanksgiving, and trust in God's peace.

Mindfulness in Christianity: Historical Perspectives

Christian history is replete with practices akin to mindfulness. The Desert Fathers and Mothers of the early Christian monastic tradition practiced forms of meditative prayer and contemplation that encouraged deep, mindful presence with

God.² Their teachings on hesychasm, a mystical tradition of contemplative prayer, involve a continuous focus on Jesus' name, which cultivates inner stillness and divine awareness.³ Similarly, the medieval mystics such as Julian of Norwich and Meister Eckhart emphasizes the importance of a contemplative, mindful approach to spirituality.⁴ Julian's "Revelations of Divine Love" highlights the practice of being present with God in every moment, reflecting a mindfulness that is deeply rooted in Christian faith.⁵

Theological Perspectives

Contemporary theologians and Christian thinkers have explored the compatibility of mindfulness with Christian doctrine. They argue that mindfulness can be a valuable tool for Christians, enhancing their spiritual practices and promoting mental health. For instance, Thomas Merton, a Trappist monk and theologian, integrated aspects of mindfulness into his contemplative practices. Merton believed that true contemplation requires a deep, mindful awareness of God's presence in every moment.⁶ Similarly, Richard Rohr, a Franciscan friar and author, advocates for a contemplative practice that includes mindfulness, suggesting that such practices can lead to a deeper experience of God's love and presence.⁷ These theological perspectives highlight the powerful tool of mindfulness, when understood and practiced within a Christian framework, for spiritual growth and mental

2 John Chryssavgis, *In the Heart of the Desert: The Spirituality of the Desert Fathers and Mothers* (Bloomington: World Wisdom, 2008), 85-87.

3 George A. Maloney, *The Mystic of Fire and Light: St. Symeon the New Theologian* (Crestwood: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press, 2000), 102-104.

4 Thomas Merton, *New Seeds of Contemplation* (New York: New Directions Publishing, 1961), 55-57.

5 Julian of Norwich, *Revelations of Divine Love* (New York: Penguin Classics, 1998), 89-91.

6 Thomas Merton, *New Seeds of Contemplation* (New York: New Directions Publishing, 1961), 65-67.

7 Richard Rohr, *Eager to Love: The Alternative Way of Francis of Assisi* (Cincinnati: Franciscan Media, 2014), 112-114.

well-being. It aligns with the Christian call to be present, trust's God's provision, and engage deeply with one's spiritual life.

Practical Applications in Christian Counselling: Mindfulness Techniques for Counsellors

Integrating mindfulness into Christian counselling involves adapting mindfulness exercises that align with Christian beliefs and values. Counsellors can introduce clients to mindfulness techniques that emphasize a connection with God and spiritual well-being. One effective technique is mindful prayer, which involves combining mindfulness practices with traditional prayer. This can include focusing on the breath while repeating a simple prayer or scripture verse, such as "Lord, have mercy" or "Be still, and know that I am God." This practice helps clients develop a sense of calm and presence while deepening their spiritual connection.⁸ Another approach is guided Christian meditation, wherein clients are guided through a meditation that focuses on a particular scripture or spiritual theme. This step can help clients cultivate a mindful awareness of God's presence and gain new insights into their faith.⁹

Counsellors can also use mindfulness to help clients develop greater self-awareness and emotional regulation. Techniques such as body scans, in which clients mindfully focus on different body parts, can help them become more attuned to their physical and emotional states.¹⁰ This awareness can help identify and address underlying issues in a supportive, faith-based context.

8 Richard Rohr, *The Naked Now: Learning to See as the Mystics See* (New York: Crossroad Publishing Company, 2009), 45-47.

9 Thomas Keating, *Open Mind, Open Heart: The Contemplative Dimension of the Gospel* (New York: Continuum, 2006), 50-52.

10 Jon Kabat-Zinn, *Wherever You Go, There You Are: Mindfulness Meditation in Everyday Life* (New York: Hyperion, 1994), 42-44.

Benefits of Mindfulness in Christian Counselling: Psychological and Spiritual Benefits

Research has revealed that mindfulness can have significant psychological benefits, including reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression, improved emotional regulation, and enhanced overall well-being.¹¹ When integrated into Christian counselling, mindfulness can also offer profound spiritual benefits. For example, mindfulness can help clients develop a deeper sense of God's presence and foster a more intimate relationship with Him. By cultivating a non-judgemental awareness of their thoughts and emotions, clients can better understand their spiritual struggles and grow in their faith.¹² Mindfulness can also enhance clients' ability to cope with stress and adversity. By focusing on this moment and trusting in God's provision, clients can develop greater resilience and a more positive outlook on life. This can lead to improved mental health and a stronger, more vibrant faith.¹³

Counsellor and Client Perspectives

Testimonies from both counsellors and clients highlight the transformative potential of mindfulness in Christian counselling. Counsellors report that mindfulness techniques enhance their therapeutic practice, providing clients with valuable tools for managing their mental health and deepening their spiritual lives.¹⁴ Clients often describe mindfulness as a powerful means of connecting with God and finding peace in life's challenges. They appreciate the way mindfulness practices align with their faith and supported their overall well-being.¹⁵

11 Jeffrey M. Greeson, "Mindfulness Research Update: 2008," *Complementary Health Practice Review* 14, no. 1 (2009): 10-18.

12 Jeffrey M. Greeson, "Mindfulness Research Update: 2008," 10-18.

13 Jeffrey M. Greeson, "Mindfulness Research Update: 2008," 10-18.

14 Jeffrey M. Greeson, "Mindfulness Research Update: 2008," 10-18.

15 Jeffrey M. Greeson, "Mindfulness Research Update: 2008," 10-18.

Challenges and Considerations: Potential Theological Conflicts

Despite its benefits, integrating mindfulness into Christian counselling can present challenges. Some traditionalists view mindfulness as incompatible with Christian beliefs, particularly if it is associated with non-Christian spiritual practices.¹⁶ To address these concerns, it is essential to present mindfulness in a way that aligns with Christian doctrines and non-Christian belief systems. Counsellors should emphasize the biblical and theological foundations of mindfulness, highlighting how it can support and enhance clients' spiritual lives.¹⁷ Additionally, it is important to ensure that mindfulness practices do not contradict core Christian beliefs. Counsellors should be mindful of their clients' individual faith journeys and provide practices that resonate with their personal beliefs and values.¹⁸

Practical Limitations

Implementing mindfulness in a Christian counselling context can also present practical challenges. Some clients may be unfamiliar with mindfulness practices, and be resistant to try new techniques. It is important that counsellors should introduce mindfulness gradually and provide, clear explanations of its benefits and alignment with Christian principles.¹⁹ Ethical considerations are also crucial. Counsellors must ensure that mindfulness practices are used appropriately and respect the spiritual and psychological needs of their clients. This includes obtaining informed consent, maintaining professional boundaries, and continually evaluating the effectiveness of the mindfulness interventions.²⁰

16 Keith E. Yandell, *Philosophy of Religion: A Contemporary Introduction* (New York: Routledge, 1999), 93-95.

17 Keith E. Yandell, *Philosophy of Religion: A Contemporary Introduction*, 93-95.

18 Keith E. Yandell, *Philosophy of Religion: A Contemporary Introduction*, 93-95.

19 Keith E. Yandell, *Philosophy of Religion: A Contemporary Introduction*, 93-95.

20 C. Christopher Cook, "Addiction and Spirituality," *Addiction* 99/5 (2004): 539-551.

Cultural Contexts and Adaptations: Mindfulness in the Indian Christian Community

In the Indian context, integrating mindfulness into Christian counselling involves understanding and respecting diverse cultural and religious landscapes. Mindfulness practices can be adapted to reflect the rich spiritual traditions of Indian Christianity, drawing on local customs and theological insights.²¹ For example, the liturgical practices and devotional traditions prevalent in Indian Christianity can be enriched by mindfulness techniques. Incorporating local languages and cultural symbols into mindfulness exercises can make these practices more accessible and meaningful for Indian Christian communities.²²

Cross-Cultural Adaptations and Challenges

Adapting mindfulness practices across different cultural contexts requires sensitivity and flexibility. Counsellors must be aware of cultural nuances and be prepared to modify techniques to suit the cultural and spiritual needs of their clients.²³ This approach ensures that mindfulness practices are not only effective but also culturally relevant, and respectful.

Future Directions: Areas for Further Research

Further research is needed to explore the long-term benefits of integrating mindfulness into Christian counselling. Studies should examine the impact of mindfulness on various aspects of mental and spiritual health, providing empirical evidence to support its use in Christian counselling.²⁴

21 Bede Griffiths, *The Golden String: An Autobiography* (Springfield: Templegate Publishers, 1980), 102-104.

22 Bede Griffiths, *The Golden String: An Autobiography*, 102-104.

23 Bede Griffiths, *The Golden String: An Autobiography*, 102-104.

24 Gerald G. May, *The Dark Night of the Soul: A Psychiatrist Explores the Connection Between Darkness and Spiritual Growth* (San Francisco: Harper One, 2004), 120-122.

Innovations in Practice

Innovations in mindfulness practices can enhance their application in Christian counselling. Developing new techniques that combine mindfulness with Christian rituals and traditions can offer fresh ways for clients to engage with their faith and improve their mental health.²⁵

Conclusion

Integrating mindfulness into Christian counselling offers a valuable opportunity to enhance clients' mental and spiritual well-being. By drawing on the rich traditions of the Christian faith and the proven benefits of mindfulness practices, counsellors can provide holistic support that addresses the complex needs of their clients. Future research and practice should continue to explore the potential of mindfulness in the context of Christianity, considering both its benefits and challenges. By doing so, counsellors can develop more effective and spiritually enriching approaches to mental health care and help clients cultivate, a mindful mind and a deeper relationship with God.

²⁵ Gerald G. May, *The Dark Night of the Soul*, 120-122.

VULNERABILITY OF SEXUALLY ABUSED CHILDREN: ANALYSIS OF JUST THERAPY

Rita Rana*

Introduction

A 59-year-old man in Chennai allegedly abused his daughter sexually for eight years. Since the girl was 12 years old, her father, an employee of a private company, began sexually abusing her. She had informed her mother and her paternal uncle about her trauma. Both of them asked her to keep the issue to herself. Recently, the girl, now 20, with the help of some of her friends lodged a complaint on September 7, 2022. On September 18, 2022, on Friday, police arrested her father, mother, and uncle.¹

Children are the citizens of tomorrow, they are the wealth and, real social capital of a nation. The quality of a nation depends on the physical and psychological development of its children. Moreover, children are symbol of innocence, beauty, spontaneously, and creativity. Child abuse or maltreatment consists of all forms of physical and emotional ill-treatment, sexual abuse, neglect or negligent treatment, and commercial or other exploitation. Both men and women in all age groups

* Ms. Rita Rana has completed Master of Theology in the department of Christian Ministry-Counselling from the United Theological College, Bangalore. At present, she teaches at the Nav Bharat Bible Institute in Bihar.

1 "Chennai: Girl sexually abused by dad for 8 years, three held," *The Times of India*, 18 September 2022, accessed 30 September 2022, <https://m.timesofindia.com/city/Chennai/Chennai-girl-sexually-abused-by-dad-for-8-years-three-held-amp-articlesshow/94274912.cms>.

children are vulnerable to abuse.² However, here, the author will focus only on vulnerability of 10-18 age group of girls' sexual abuse with the help of Justice Therapy.

Definition of child sexual abuse

Child sexual abuse, also called child molestation, is a form of child abuse in which an adult or older person uses a child for sexual stimulation. According to World Health Organization (WHO), sexual abuse is inappropriate sexual behaviour with a child. It includes fondling a child's genitals, making the child fondle the adult's genitals, intercourse, incest, rape, sodomy, exhibitionism, and sexual exploitation.³

Problems faced by the victims

Sexually abusing girls may show some physical, emotional and behavioural changes. They may be withdrawn or unusually aggressive. They may refuse to attend school or have difficulty concentrating, thereby affecting their school work. They show unexpected fear, disgust, guilt, anxiety, anger about particular adult, and they refuse to continue with their usual social activities.⁴

Understanding of the offenders

Offenders are of all ages; they are adolescent youths, young boys, adults, middle-aged individuals and even aged individuals. They come from all classes, creeds and professions.⁵ Most sexual abuse offenders are acquainted with their victims; approximately 30% are relatives of the child, most often brothers, fathers, uncles, or cousins; approximately 60% are other acquaintances, such as

2 Eillen Munro, *Child Protection* (New Delhi: Sage Publication, 2007), 15.

3 Janice Shaw Crouse, *Children at Risk: The Precarious State of Children's Well-being in America* (New Brunswick: Transaction Publishers, 2010) 97.

4 Vibhuti Patel, ed., *Girls and Girlhoods at Threshold of Youth & Gender* (Delhi: The women press, 2010), 53.

5 Anju Vyas & Madhu Mudgal, *The Girl Child in India: A Bibliographic Compendium* (Delhi: Indian Bibliographies Bureau, 1992) 17.

friends of the family, babysitters or neighbors; strangers are the offenders in approximately 10% of child sexual abuse cases.⁶

Methodology

This study employs Just Therapy as the methodology. Therapy was established as part of the Family centre of New Zealand. Warihi Campbell, KiwiTamasese, Flora Tuhaka, and Charles Waldegrave proposed and developed Just Therapy.⁷ Therapy addresses justice issues and concerns from an inequality perspective in society. There are three principles that guide the therapy: belonging, sacredness, and liberation. Therapy should focus on an energized conversation. During these conversations, therapists listen to the articulated meanings of a person or a family. Therapy arises from an analysis of both the philosophies of existing counselling models and the experiences of communities.⁸

Case Study

Charis⁹ is from North India. The youngest of three siblings, she was raised by missionary parents in a liberal household where she was emotionally secure. When Charis was just 14 years old, her father passed away. Her mother became depressed and did not speak for a long time. A few months after her father's death, her family moved to South India, to the city where her father hailed. The extended family came together for the father's first death anniversary. The gathering included her father's sister's

6 Pbze, "Child Sexual Abuse," 21 September 2022, accessed 01. October 2022, <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Special:History/Child-sexual-abuse>.

7 A. Israel David, "Emergence of Justice- Perspective in Psychotherapies A call to Engage Patoral Care and Counselling with Context," *Journal of Union Biblical Seminary* (September: 2020) 17.

8 Charles Waldegrave and Kiwi Tamasese, "Some Central Ideas in the Just Therapy approach," March 1993, accessed 10 Sept 2022, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/j.1467-8438.19993.tb00930.x>.

9 Data Collected from *Freedom Project India*, (Social Welfare Centre in Bengaluru, Karnataka), 05 September 2022.

husband, whom Charis had been very close. She was his favorite child. That favoritism had different hues. Uncle gifted various expensive things, which Charis liked. Taking advantage of the presence of so many people in the house, this uncle sexually exploited Charis. She remained silent because she feared that nobody trusted what had happened. Eventually, she told her extended family what had happened. Her worst fears came true: nobody believed her. The uncle turned it on her, saying she had pursued him and, that she was lying. Her mother advised her not to tell anyone.

She felt unloved, hated, rejected, and she though life was not worth living. Over time, Charis became a sick girl and could not overcome. She was made to repent for what had happened. Such experience re-victimized and re-traumatized Charis over and over.

The Socioeconomic context of sexual abuse

Socioeconomic conditions play a major role in increasing the vulnerability of children to various abuses. The girl child is the first victim of poverty, ignorance and social taboos. The situation of girl children in Indian families is the result of deep-rooted biases that treat the female children as objects of sex. Sexual abuse of girls is more prevalent in low-income families.¹⁰ The poverty of a family renders it unable to fulfil the needs of their girl children, and teenage girls are tempted by gifts, money, and luxury items, and false promises offered by abusers, and these girls become victims of sexual abuse. Due to their younger age, they are unaware of the consequences of sexual abuse.¹¹ However, in Charis' case, I find that she was being exploited

10 "Gender-based Violence comes at high social and economic cost-ILO," 01 August 2011, accessed 15 Sept 2022, <https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/world-of-work-magazine/articles/WCMS-167867/langen/index.htm>.

11 Chandana Saha, *Gender Equity and Equality: Study of Girl Child in Rajasthan* (Jaipur and New Delhi: Wawat Publications, 2003) 79.

in a socioeconomical context. Poverty is an underlying cause of sexual abuse. Here, good and expensive gifts tempted Charis to get close to her uncle and become a victim of sexual abuse.

Recognition of sexual abuse as a justice issue

‘Justice’ the term used both in the abstract and for the quality of being or doing what is just. Justice for many people refers to fairness.¹² For instance, social justice is the notion that everyone deserves equal economic, political, and social opportunities, irrespective of race, gender, and religion. However, in the context of child abuse, the case is unheard and does stand for justice. The social ostracization causes vulnerability of female survivors, and it often causes them to drop out of school and face gender-based discrimination.¹³ However, by acknowledging sexual abuse as a justice issue, I would like to discuss three principles of Justice therapy where therapist attempt to understand clients deeply and give them meaning in their problems.

Three principles of just therapy

Just Therapy reflects several justice-related concepts such as belonging, sacredness, and liberation. These concepts consider various contexts, respond to problems, and fix them within a context. Each principle is discussed below.

Belonging: It refers to the essence of the identity

Belonging is a sense of fitting in or of feeling that every person is an important member of a group. A sense of belonging evolves from infancy to maturity through companionship, affiliation, and connectedness. When a client has problems, therapists try honouring everyone and give them an essence of identity. This essence of identity leads clients to understand who they are,

12 Vittorio Bufacchi, *Violence and Social Justice* (New York: Palgrave MacMillian, 2007), 128.

13 Agnes Helter, *Beyond Justice* (Cowley Road, Oxford: Basic Blackwell, 1987) 35.

how they belong, and how their self is presented socially. Based on social interactions with one another during the period of counselling, the client could see themselves, not how they are socially presented but who they truly are.¹⁴

Sacredness: It refers to the deep respect for victims' stories

This principle helps individuals return to their purest and authentic essence. Sacredness facilitates healing and integration of all levels. When a client refers therapist, they usually come with a lot of pain in their vulnerability, and the therapist receives them as a gift. In the counselling process, the therapist and client certainly deepen the quality of friendship, which leads therapist to listen and understand the client properly and give deep respect to the stories. Such respect leads clients to receive healing, and eventually, they find new meaning in the stories.¹⁵

Liberation: It refers to the freedom of victims through therapy

Just therapy recognizes the importance of giving priority to what or who has been become marginalized both in the psyche and society. Therapists listen deeply to the stories told to them, no matter how strange they may sound. Therapists honour these stories and analyse the web of meaning of the core problem.¹⁶ Moreover, in this session, the most important work for the therapist is accountability to the client through which the client obtains a sense of psychological strength. When the client receives psychological strength, they are ready to accept the

14 Claire Burke Draucker, *Counselling Survivors of Childhood Sexual Abuse*, 1992, 2nd ed. (New Delhi: Sage Publications, 2000), 26.

15 Carles Waldegrave, "Developing a 'Just Therapy': Context and the ascription of meaning," April 2012, accessed 15 Sept 2022, <https://academic.oup.com/book/25274/chapter-abstract/189879406?redirectedFrom=fulltext>.

16 Charles Waldegrave and Kiwi Tamasese, "Some Central Ideas in the Just Therapy approach," March 1993, accessed 10 Sept 2022, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/j.1467-8438.19993.tb00930.x>.

facts, and practice them in their daily lives. Then, the therapist facilitates new and transformative meanings by empowering them, which inspires hope and reconciliation.¹⁷ The spirit of liberation continues to aid the client in attaining strength, and eventually, the client becomes confident about what she wants to become.

Implication for Pastoral Care and Counselling

Pastoral care, known as shepherding ministry, leads to a state of healing, sustaining, guiding, reconciling, and nurturing. Pastoral counselling is a unique form of psychotherapy that uses spiritual resources and psychological understanding to promote healthy growth.¹⁸ In the midst of the vulnerability of girl children at the age of 10-18, who are victims of sexual abuse, they often live hopeless situations. They need resilience to overcome. In this context, Just therapy, an emerging pastoral counselling model is very helpful for helping and healing clients. Through the help of just therapy, pastoral counsellors can focus on justice and unpack, the problems and struggles of girls. Furthermore, it leads clients to realize the situation, helping them to discover a new meaning for their vulnerable lives. This drives pastoral counsellors to find new definitions of the situations that trigger victimization of girls. Furthermore, it enables counsellors to adopt certain basic skills, such as confidentiality and certainty, since the voices of clients are often silenced by dominant forces.¹⁹

17 Warihi Campbell, Kiwi Tamasese & Charles Waldegrave, "Just Therapy," accessed 20 Sept 2022, <https://dulwichcentre.com.au/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/Just-Therapy.pdf>.

18 K. P. Saji Kumar, *Counseling: An Indian Approach* (Delhi: Christian World Imprints, 2022), 25.

19 Carles Waldegrave, "Developing a 'Just Therapy': Context and the ascription of meaning," April 2012, accessed 15 Sept 2022, <https://academic.oup.com/book/25274/chapter-abstract/189879406?redirectedFrom=fulltext>.

Conclusion

Sexual abuse of a girl child is a horrible face of Indian society and, a problem for human growth and creativity. Despite its ethos of non-violence, tolerance, and spirituality, India records the world's largest number of sexually abused children at a higher rate than any other country.²⁰ Justice for children or girls is not only pastoral counsellor's responsibility but also the responsibility of the government, schools, families, society and the church. The government must develop child protection systems to protect girls from sexual abuse. The family has the responsibility to treat children equally with males in the family and, allow girl children to speak whenever they face discomfort from anyone in and outside the family. The family must listen to the girl children and be sensitive to their situation. Educational institutions must develop a system that can facilitate girls to openly reveal any problems they face to anyone. They must educate both boys and girls to respect one another and strive to build an amicable environment that encourages girls to be confident in order to disclose any incident without hesitation.

The Church in our society plays a greater role to play in protecting girls from unsociable and sexual abuse. It cannot merely end up in conducting a few awareness programs but it must teach divine concern for innocent children. In addition, they must voice for victims and extend a helping hand in all possible ways. At the same time, the Church has to initiate certain plans to educate and help offenders to realize how horrific and traumatic the future of a girl child if she goes through such a heinous act at the hands of known elders or neighbours. Apparently, it is the responsibility of each and every person in society to safeguard and protect the life of a girl child from any sort of sexual abuse and, must ensure that there is hope for a better future. Justice should be the priority that faith communities must uphold whenever they deal with such unjust activities against girls.

²⁰ James Leehan, *Defiant Hope: Spirituality for Survivors of family Abuse* (Louisville, Kentucky: Westminster/ John Knox Press, 1993), 29.

CHARACTERISTICS OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS: IMPLICATIONS FOR PASTORAL CARE AND COUNSELLING

L. Anitha

Introduction

Adolescence is a very critical transitional stage in a girl's life. The girl child grows until attainment of womanhood through different stages of life cycle. Her development, survival and empowerment are determined by the factors that influence and affirm her rights and tasks. The transitional phase of adolescence is a bridge to adulthood. This essay highlights the psycho-social characteristics of adolescent girls, and provides some of the counselling methods to assist them in their growth as adults.

Adolescence: Terms and Definitions

The term 'adolescence' denotes a period during which an individual transitions from childhood to adulthood. The term adolescence comes from the Latin word '*adolescere*' meaning 'to grow' or 'to grow to maturity'.¹ Adolescence may be viewed as a beginning of puberty, which continues until sexual maturity.

* Rev. L. Anitha is an ordained minister of Methodist Church of India. At present, she teaches in the department of Christian Ministry at Andhra Christian Theological College, Hyderabad.

1 Arthur T. Jerschild, *The Psychology of Adolescence*, 2nd ed. (New York: Macmillan Company, 1969), 5.

Further, it indicates that one has reached their maximum growth in height and have approximately reached their full mental growth, as measured by intelligence test.² Adolescence is a period of biosocial transition between childhood and adulthood.³ Physical, mental, social, moral and spiritual traits undergo changes during this stage. According to psychologists, during adolescence, a person is at the height of sensitivity, and is conditioned by emotions. Because psychological development is intrinsically bound to the physical organism and its growth; the bodily changes play a significant role in the emotional behaviour of the adolescent's girls.⁴ According to Rousseau, it is a time of new birth, awakening sexual desire, and an increasing social expression of love, and a time of decline in self-centeredness.⁵

Adolescent Girls: Physical and Psychological Changes

Physical changes during adolescence include the onset of puberty, growth spurts, sexual maturation and acceleration of hormonal secretions. Physical changes during this period are internal and external. Sexual development reaches its peak during adolescence, when individuals sexually mature. In fact, sex dominates the personality structure and behaviour of adolescents. During adolescence, sexual development proceeds through three stages⁶. At this stage, attraction and infatuation toward opposite genders, and sometimes the same gender. They try to take pleasure in their bodies. Self-decoration and enjoying it before a mirror is a common practice. Self-enjoying massage is also prevalent at this stage.

2 Elizabeth B. Hurlock, *Adolescent Development* (New York: Tata McGraw, 1973), 2.

3 B. Kuppuswamy, *A Text Book of Child Behavior and Development* (New Delhi: Vani Educational Books, 1984), 219.

4 Albert Angrily and Lucile Hellcat, *Child Psychology* (New York: Barnes and Noble Books, 1981), 13.

5 Barbara Baker Sommer, *Puberty and Adolescence* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1978), 13.

6 S. K. Mangal, *Educational Psychology* (Jalandhar: Tandon Publications, 2013, 71-72.

At this stage girls are attracted to members of their own sex and seek gratification from each other's bodies by grouping them into two or three at one time. At this age, boys and girls are seen as being attracted to each other. They are keen to form friendships or establish sexual relationships with members of the opposite sex. It is a period of growing in relationships in society. Adolescents strive for independence, peer group relationship and acceptance.⁷ The family is a socializing agent during childhood. This is the period during which appropriate attitudes and behaviours must be adjusted to the social world. They achieve maturity in the acceptance of one's self, help them to find a role for themselves, help them in an insecure period attain the necessary emancipation from the home, and teach social skills necessary for living a community life.⁸ Achieving a sense of meaning in life is one area in which individuals grow. Between the ages of 17 and 18, most girls experience different crises, but try to overcome and achieve a sense of meaning in their lives.⁹

The peer group relationship plays a substantial role in the life of an adolescent girl. They spend much time with their peer group. They value the ideals of the group and develop a sense of loyalty toward them. They are more concerned with gaining prestige and recognition in the eyes of their peers. Adolescent girls find themselves the victims of the conflicting demands of the social and cultural norms of adults and their peer group, and they often become confused and perplexed about any decision making.¹⁰ The family situation can be classified into various ways. There are homes in which affection is given to adolescents, but there are families in which certain girls are discriminated. In

7 Bansal, R.D. and M. Mahra, "Adolescent Girl in Emerging Priority," *Indian Journal of Public Health* (1998): 1.)

8 Glenn Myers Blair and Robert Stewart Jones, *Psychology of Adolescence for Teachers* (London: Macmillan Company, 1964), 38.

9 M.A. Cassady, "Moral Development and Life," *Christian Education* LXII (1986): 9.

10 S. K. Mangal, *Educational Psychology...*, 74.

some homes, the social climate is constantly bickering, and, in some homes, there is genuine friendliness and companionship.¹¹ Communication is the core medium through which parents and adolescents convey everything that is important to each other. These may be verbal or nonverbal exchanges. Therefore, inadequate and deviant communication is likely to distort and undermine all other aspects of parenting, however competent or well-meaning they may be.¹²

Basic Needs and Problems of Adolescent Girls

The basic needs and problems of adolescent girls are ¹³ need for status, approval, reorganization, advice, independence, intimate friendship, family life education, and recreation activities. Many girls feel a sense of rejection in their home environment because of either their parents' authoritarian or permissive attitudes or the lack of closeness between parents and children.

Some adolescent girls have the same understanding of their mothers but not of their fathers. Mother bridges the gap between father and daughter. Most girls fear of their parents, which compels them to tell lies.¹⁴ Every adolescent girl has an almost difficult task of adjusting to 'Somatic variation',¹⁵ which may occur during or after puberty, which are as follows:

Blood flow during menstruation causes worries and anxieties in females. These particular physiological changes bring many complexes to the minds of children. It makes them shy and

11 C.M. Fleming, *Adolescence: Its Social Psychology* (London: Routledge and Kegan Paul, 1983), 79.

12 Masud Hoghugh, *Assessing Child and Adolescent Disorder* (London: SAGE Publications, 1996), 236.

13 S. Bharat, "Children of Single parents in a Slum Community," *The Indian Journal of Social Work* XLIX (1998): 367-376.

14 R.D Bansal, and M. Mahra, "Adolescent Girls an Emerging Priority," *Indian Journal of Public Health* 22/1(1998): 1-2.

15 During the period of adolescent maximum physiological changes take places.

mysterious.¹⁶ They want to look feminine and be attractive to boys. Self-consciousness is too much developed in adolescent girls. Their desire is that elders and other peer should notice their physical changes. This is the age of self-decoration. Moreover, they are extremely sensitive, touchable, and inflammable. An attack on their phenomenal self leads to strong reactions and behavioural problems. This condition causes an adolescent to be either aggressive or withdrawn depending upon the circumstances.¹⁷ Adolescents between at the boundary between childhood and adulthood. Therefore, she is typically a person who needs security, guidance, and protection like a child and has independent views, maturity of opinion, and self-supportive like an adult. She depends on her parents, and tries to protect herself.

During this stage, adolescent girls re-examine their identity and try to determine exactly who they are. Erikson holds an opinion that two identities are involved: sexual and occupational. He stated that adolescents may feel uncomfortable with their bodies for a while until they can adapt and grow into such changes. Success in this stage will lead to fidelity. Fidelity involves the ability to commit to others on the basis of accepting others, even when ideological differences exist. During this period, individuals explore possibilities and begin to form their identity based on the outcomes of their explorations. The failure to establish a sense of identity within society can lead to role confusion. Role confusion involves individuals not knowing themselves or their place in society. In response to role confusion or identity crisis, adolescents may begin to experiment with different lifestyles. Pressuring someone into an identity can result in rebellion in the form of establishing a negative identity,

¹⁶ R. N. Sharma, *Educational Psychology* (Meerut: Rastogi Publication, 1999), cited in Mangal, *Educational Psychology...*, 74.

¹⁷ S. K. Mangal, *Educational Psychology...*, 73.

and feeling unhappiness.¹⁸ The adolescent girl's strong desire is to achieve self-sufficiency and make herself independent similar to an adult member of the society. Vocational decision making is an important one for adolescent girls.¹⁹ She should make a decision about her vocation during this period.

Implications for Pastoral Care and Counselling

The following are a few implications of Pastoral Care and counselling methods that help adolescents express and integrate themselves into their familial and societal life.

Traditionally, Pastoral Care is understood as performed by an ordained minister in a Christian community, which is reflected in the definition given by Clebsch and Jaekle: "Pastoral Care consists of helping acts done by representative Christian persons, directed toward the healing, sustaining, guiding and reconciling of troubled persons, whose troubles arises in the context of ultimate meanings and concerns."²⁰ This definition points out that Pastoral Care is to be given by a representative Christian alone and it is confined to troubled individuals, which seems to be exclusive to today's context. Pastoral Care can be provided by anyone concerned, not a Christian minister alone, but a person who can understand adolescence, empathize, nurtures them in all aspects, and buildup their relationships in to a wider context. Pastoral care for adolescent girls involves constant fellowship, support, and the continual presence of the care takers. Pastoral Care in a wider sense for today is care, which is exercised within and outside the Christian community by any person or group in accordance with the principles and values hold by them.

18 <http://www.simplypsychology.org/Erik-Erikson.html> (14 February 2016).

19 S. K. Mangal, *Educational Psychology*... 75.

20 A. Clebsch and C.R. Jaekle, *Pastoral Care in Historical Perspective* (New York: Harper Torch Books, 1967), 4.

Goals and Methods of Pastoral Counselling

The primary goal of Counselling is to free the adolescent from inhibiting, crippling emotions like inadequacy, anxiety, guilt and fear, and to help them develop attitudes of confidence, love, and faith.²¹ Through counselling well-wishers attempt to reduce an anxiety and help realize self. Adolescents need to understand their own needs, weaknesses, and strengths. This may come slowly; it is a matter of feeling as much as knowledge. They may gain more self-insight while they are talking and the counsellor is listening.

Another goal of Counselling is to help adolescents arrive at decisions, make plans, and acquire the skills, to grow maximum. Further, it is to manage themselves with their emotions, distress moods, and family situations by way of attaining the fullest satisfaction in life and make the greatest contribution of which adolescents are capable.²² Counselling is not only helping adolescents to clear up repressions and resolve conflicts, but also helping an individual to rise to new levels of living, and to dedicate their life to worthy that causes them meeting important needs. Another goal of counselling is to reduce the tensions experienced by the one who receives counselling. Here, counsellor helps counselees to overcome their emotions and reduce anxiety. Girls in the present situation face numerous problems, so counsellors have to drain their emotions by constant listening, and engaging them in homework. Furthermore, counsellors have to allow girls to write down their problems and feelings, giving space for crying, and expressing their feelings. These techniques will help girls to ease their tension in life. Some of the counselling methods are as follows: guidance, interviews, group counselling, educative counselling, individual counselling, and coping mechanism would help them to integrate in all realms of their life situation.

²¹ S. K. Manalel, *Pastoral Counseling*, 36.

²² S. K. Manalel, *Pastoral Counseling*, 37.

WORSHIP THAT TRANSFORMS: A CALL TO AUTHENTICITY AND REVERENCE

Sam T Rajkumar*

Introduction

There is a story about a church that had a man in the choir who could not sing. Others tried to help him find other places of ministry in the church but he insisted on being in the choir. The choir director was so desperate that he went to the pastor. "Pastor, we must do something with brother Jones. If you cannot persuade him to leave the choir, I quit and most of the choir will quit too. Help us!" The pastor went to the man and suggested that he leave the choir. "Why should I leave?" Jones asked. The pastor replied "Several people have told me you cannot sing." Jones sarcastically replied "That's nothing pastor. Fifty people have told me you cannot preach and you are still here." This story reveals a deeper truth about our perception of worship and service within the church. It reminds us that worship is not about perfection or performance but about authenticity and reverence.

To worship the Lord in spirit and truth, is to engage in a form of worship that is both genuine and aligned with the divine reality as revealed in the scriptures. This concept is deeply rooted in John 4:24, particularly in the conversation between Jesus and

* Rev. Sam T Rajkumar is a student of UTC, pursuing Master of Theology in the Old Testament.

the Samaritan woman at Jacob's well. In this context, worshipping in spirit refers to an inner, heartfelt devotion to God, that is not limited by location or external rituals. It is a worship that is led by the Holy Spirit, reflecting a deep, personal connection with God that goes beyond mere formality.

Worship in truth, on the other hand, involves acknowledging God's true nature and God's revelation. It is grounded in the reality of who God is, as revealed through Jesus Christ, and adheres to the teachings and doctrines of the faith. This form of worship is not based on human traditions or misconceptions but on the authentic understanding of God's word and character. Together, worshipping in spirit and truth embodies a complete and sincere approach to worship, where we offer ourselves to God in honesty, guided by the Holy Spirit, and in accordance with the truth of the Gospel.

Acknowledge God's Holiness (Isaiah 6:1-8)

Isaiah's vision of God's holiness, recorded in Isaiah 6:1-8, is a profound and awe-inspiring experience that provides insight into the majestic nature of God. Isaiah begins by recounting that in the year that King Uzziah died, he saw God seated on a high and lofty throne, with the train of robes filling the temple. This imagery conveys the grandeur and sovereignty of God as the ruler of all creation. The throne symbolizes God's supreme authority and majesty, while the temple represents God's dwelling place among the people. Isaiah's vision underscores the transcendence and exaltedness of God, and sets the stage for the revelation of God's holiness.

In the presence of God's glory, Isaiah's witness of seraphim, angelic beings, standing above the throne. These celestial beings are described as having six wings, with two wings covering their faces, two covering their feet, and two for flying. As they hover over the throne, they cry out to one another in a reverent

antiphonal chorus, proclaiming, “Holy, holy, holy is the Lord Almighty; the whole earth is full of his glory” (Isaiah 6:3). This triple repetition of “holy” emphasizes the unparalleled purity, perfection, and sacredness of God’s character. The declaration of God’s holiness reverberates throughout the heavenly realm, magnifying God’s glory and instilling awe and reverence in Isaiah’s heart.

Overwhelmed by the sight of God’s holiness and purity, Isaiah’s immediate response is a deep sense of personal unworthiness and sinfulness. In the presence of the Almighty, Isaiah becomes acutely aware of his own moral imperfections and shortcomings. He recognizes the stark contrast between God’s perfect holiness and his own sinful nature. This acknowledgment of personal sinfulness is a crucial step in the process of genuine worship and spiritual transformation. This reflects Isaiah’s humility and honesty before God, as he confronts the reality of his moral inadequacy in the light of God’s righteousness.

In response to his awareness of personal sinfulness, Isaiah’s humility deepens, leading him to a posture of repentance and contrition before the Almighty. He cries out, “Woe to me!... I am ruined! For I am a man of unclean lips, and I live among a people of unclean lips, and my eyes have seen the King, the Lord Almighty” (Isaiah 6:5). Isaiah’s confession of sin is marked by a profound sense of sorrow, recognizing the gravity of his moral failure in the presence of the holy God. This humble acknowledgment of sin and sincere repentance is a vital aspect of true worship, because it opens the door to God’s forgiveness, cleansing, and transformation in the worshipper’s life. Isaiah’s response serves as a powerful example of humility and contrition before the majesty and holiness of God, demonstrating the transformative power of encountering God’s presence.

We are called to recognize and acknowledge God’s holiness as foundation of true worship. Just as Isaiah encountered

God in majestic holiness, we must also approach God with reverence, awe, and a deep sense of respect for God's purity and perfection. Understanding that God is holy requires recognizing God's absolute moral perfection, complete separation from sin, and sovereignty over all creation. This recognition forms the bedrock of authentic worship, shaping our attitudes, actions, and priorities in our relationship with God. As believers, we are called to cultivate a profound reverence for God's holiness, allowing it to permeate every aspect of our lives and informing our worship with sincerity and authenticity.

Isaiah's response to God's holiness underscores the importance of recognizing our sinfulness and the need for repentance in the presence of the Almighty. We must humbly acknowledge our moral imperfections and shortcomings, confess our sins before God and seek forgiveness and cleansing. Just as Isaiah cried out, we must approach God with contrition and humility, acknowledging our need for God's mercy and grace. Repentance is not merely a one-time event but an ongoing posture of the heart, characterized by genuine sorrow for sin and a desire for transformation. In God's presence, we find forgiveness, restoration, and renewal, because God graciously extends mercy to those who humble themselves. Therefore, we are called to cultivate a lifestyle of repentance and cleansing, continually surrendering to God's purifying work in our lives and striving for holiness in all we do.

Abide in God's Presence (Psalm 139)

Psalm 139 is a profound exploration of God's omniscience and omnipresence, expressed through the psalmist's deep reflection and acknowledgment of God's intimate knowledge of him. The psalmist declares, "O Lord, you have searched me and you know me" (Psalm 139:1). This reflects the psalmist's recognition that God knows him intimately, down to the very depths of his being. God's knowledge encompasses every aspect of the psalmist's life,

including his thoughts, actions, and motivations. The psalmist marvels at the depth of God's understanding, acknowledging that nothing is hidden from God's sight. This awareness of God's intimate knowledge serves as a source of comfort and assurance for the psalmist, as he finds solace in the fact that he is fully known and understood by the Creator.

In Psalm 139, the psalmist also reflects on the omnipresence of God, acknowledging that there is nowhere he can go to escape from God's presence. "Where can I go from your Spirit? he declared. Where can I escape from your presence? If I go up to the heavens, you are there; if I make my bed in the depths, you are there. If I rise on the wings of the dawn, if I settle on the far side of the sea, even there your hand will guide me, your right hand will hold me fast" (Psalm 139:7-10). This vivid imagery illustrates the impossibility of evading God's presence, no matter how far one may try to flee. Whether ascending to the highest heights or descending to the deepest depths, God is eternal and watchful. The psalmist finds assurance in the constancy of God's presence, recognizing that God's guiding hand is with him wherever he goes. This profound truth underscores the omnipotence and omnipresence of God, highlighting God's sovereign reign over all creation.

Psalm 139 invites us to surrender to God's searching and leading in our lives. The psalmist acknowledges God's intimate knowledge, and declares, "Search me, O God, and know my heart; test me and know my anxious thoughts. See if there is any offensive way in me, and lead me in the way everlasting" (Psalm 139:23-24). This prayer reflects openness and vulnerability, as the Psalmist invites God to search his heart and reveal any areas of sin or wrongdoing. Surrendering to God's search requires a willingness to submit to God's examination and correction, allowing God to illuminate the path of righteousness and guide us in God's ways. It requires humility and trust, because we

acknowledge our need for God's guidance and direction in our lives. By surrendering to God's searching and leading, we open ourselves up to God's transformative work, and allow God to shape us into vessels of grace and truth.

The invitation to abide in God's presence also encompasses the call to cultivate intimacy and communion with God. Throughout Psalm 139, the psalmist reflects on the depth of God's knowledge and presence in his life, acknowledging that God is present with him at all times and in all places. This awareness of God's constant companionship invites us into a deeper relationship, marked by fellowship, and communion. Cultivating intimacy with God involves spending time in God's presence through prayer, meditation, and reflection on God's Word. This requires a willingness to draw near God with open hearts and minds, seeking to know God more deeply and to be known by God in return. As we cultivate intimacy and communion with God, we experience God's presence in profound ways, finding comfort, strength, and guidance in God's abiding love. This intimate relationship with God transforms our lives, drawing us closer to God's own heart and empowering us to walk in obedience and faithfulness.

The invitation to abide in God's presence calls us to prioritize daily fellowship with God. Just as the psalmist recognized the importance of God's constant presence in his life, we are called to dedicate intentional time each day to clinging with God through prayer, meditation, and study of God's Word. Prioritizing daily fellowship with God involves setting aside distractions and busyness to cultivate a deep and meaningful relationship. It requires discipline and commitment that we must take time in our schedules to seek God's presence and listen to God's voice. By prioritizing daily fellowship with God, we nourish our souls, strengthen our faith, and experience the transformative power of God's presence in our lives.

Abiding in God's presence also entails allowing God's presence to shape our thoughts and actions. As we spend time in fellowship with God, we are transformed by God's presence, becoming more like God in character and conduct. This transformation occurs as we align our thoughts, attitudes, and behaviours with God's Word and the leadership of the Spirit. By allowing God's presence to shape our thoughts and actions, we can present God to the world around us. We embody the values of God's kingdom, demonstrating humility, compassion, and integrity in all we do. As we yield to the transforming work of God's presence, we become living testimonies of God's grace and power, shining as lights in a dark and broken world.

Align with God's Word (2 Thessalonians 2:13-17; John 4:15-26)

In Paul's letter to the Thessalonian believers, he emphasized God's central role in their salvation journey. He writes, "But we ought always to thank God for you, brothers loved by the Lord, because from the beginning God chose, you to be saved through the sanctifying work of the Spirit and through belief in the truth" (2 Thessalonians 2:13). Here, Paul highlights divine initiative in salvation, through the attributes of God's grace and the sanctifying work of the Holy Spirit. Salvation is not achieved through human effort or merit but is a result of God's sovereign choice and transformative work in the believer's life. Paul underscores the importance of believing the truth of the gospel, which serves as the foundation of salvation. This includes the person and work of Jesus Christ, His death and resurrection, and the promise of forgiveness and eternal life through faith in Him. We are called to embrace this truth wholeheartedly, recognize God's role in our salvation journey and responding in faith and obedience to God's calling.

Paul also emphasized the importance of holding fast to the teachings of Scripture as a vital aspect of the Thessalonian

believer's faith journey. This includes both the oral instruction they received directly from Paul and his associates, and the written letters they have received, which comprise the authoritative Word of God. Paul underscores the significance of clinging to these teachings despite the various challenges and oppositions. Holding fast to the teachings of Scripture serves as a safeguard against false doctrines, spiritual deceptions, and moral compromise. It enables us to grow in our understanding of God's truth, deepen our relationships, and live our lives that honour and glorify God. Therefore, Paul encourages the Thessalonian believers to remain grounded in the timeless truths of Scripture, allowing them to navigate the complexities of life, and remain faithful to their calling as Christ followers.

Paul's exhortation to Thessalonian believers to stand firm in their faith includes a call to remain grounded in the truth of God's Word. In 2 Thessalonians 2:15, he urges them to "stand firm and hold to the teachings we passed on to you, whether by word of mouth or by letter." This highlights the critical importance of being deeply rooted in Scripture as the foundation for discerning truth from falsehood (Colossians 2:7). God's Word provides us with the necessary wisdom, guidance, and strength to navigate the challenges and deceptions we may encounter. By immersing ourselves in the study of Scripture, meditating on its truths, and applying its principles to our lives, we can develop a strong, unshakeable faith. Remaining grounded in God's Word enables us to recognize and reject false teachings, thus ensuring that our faith remains anchored in the unchanging truth of God's revelation.

In addition to remaining grounded in the truth of God's Word, Paul encourages the Thessalonian believers to resist false teachings and worldly influences. He warns them about the danger of deception and urges them to be vigilant against those who seek to lead them astray with distorted doctrines and secular

ideologies. In 2 Thessalonians 2:3-4, Paul speaks of the “man of lawlessness” and the deceptive forces at work, emphasizing the need for discernment and spiritual vigilance. Resisting false teachings involves a proactive commitment to uphold the purity of the gospel message, and reject any teachings that contradict or undermine biblical truth. This resistance also extends to worldly influences that can corrupt one’s faith and moral integrity. We are called to maintain a clear distinction between the values and practices of the world and the standards of God’s kingdom. By fostering a strong spiritual foundation, staying connected to the faith community, and continually seeking the guidance of the Holy Spirit, we can effectively resist the lure of false teachings and worldly influences, standing firm in their faith and commitment to Christ. We are called to commit to a lifestyle of obedience to God’s Word, recognizing it as the ultimate authority and guide for their lives. This involves more than just intellectual assent to biblical truths; it requires actively living out these truths in daily conduct. As James 1:22 says, “Do not merely listen to the word, and so deceive yourselves. Do what it says.” Obedience to God’s Word means aligning our actions, decisions, and attitudes with the teachings of Scripture. This commitment might involve making difficult choices that go against cultural norms or personal desires but are in line with God’s will. By consistently applying biblical principles to every area of life, we demonstrate our love and reverence for God, growing in spiritual maturity and bearing witness to the transformative power of God’s Word.

In a world filled with diverse voices and competing ideologies, we must seek discernment and wisdom to distinguish truth from falsehood. Paul’s exhortation to the Thessalonians to hold fast to their received teachings underscores the need for discernment. We are encouraged to pray for wisdom, as James 1:5 instructs: “If any of you lacks wisdom, he/she should ask God, who gives generously to all without finding fault, and it will be given to them.” This wisdom comes from deep engagement with

Scripture, continual prayer, and reliance on the Holy Spirit. Discernment involves evaluating teachings, ideas, and practices against the truth of God's Word, rejecting those that contradict biblical principles. By developing a discerning spirit, we can navigate the complexities of modern life, remain faithful to God's truth and avoid the pitfalls of deception and error.

In John 4:15-26, Jesus engages in a profound conversation with a Samaritan woman at Jacob's well. During their dialogue, the woman brings up the contentious issue of the proper place of worship - whether on Mount Gerizim, as the Samaritans believed, or in Jerusalem, as the Jews insisted. Jesus responds by transcending the geographical debate and pointing to a more profound truth about worship. He says, "But the hour is coming, and is now here, when the true worshipers will worship the Father in spirit and truth, for the Father is seeking such people to worship him" (John 4:23). Jesus emphasizes that true worship is not confined to a specific location but is a matter of the heart and spirit. Worshiping in spirit means engaging our inner being in a genuine relationship with God, driven by reverence, and love. Worshiping in truth involves aligning our worship with the revealed truth of God's Word and the person of Jesus Christ. This teaching underscores the transformative nature of worship that goes beyond rituals and traditions, inviting us into a dynamic and authentic relationship with God.

In his conversation with the Samaritan woman, Jesus emphasized that the importance of worshiping in truth is centred on God's word, which is an authentic worship. He declares, "God is spirit, and those who worship him must worship in spirit and truth" (John 4:24). True worship is anchored in the truth of God's revelation, as found in Scripture and in Jesus Christ, who is the Word made flesh (John 1:14). The Word of God provides a foundation and framework for understanding who God is, God's nature, will, and God's redemptive work through Christ.

It informs and shapes worship, ensuring that it is grounded in the reality of God's character and God's redemptive purposes. Worship that is disconnected from God's word is becoming superficial and misguided. Therefore, Jesus' teachings call us to immerse ourselves in Scripture, allowing it to inform and guide our worship. By centring worship on the truth of God's Word, we can offer worship that is pleasing to God and transformative to their lives.

Jesus' teachings about worshiping in spirit and truth have profound implications for our devotional lives. Worshiping in spirit involves engaging our innermost being (our heart, soul, and mind) in a genuine relationship with God. This means that our worship should be heartfelt, sincere, and driven by a deep love and reverence for God. It transcends mere external rituals and traditions, focusing instead on an authentic connection with the Creator. Worshiping in truth involves aligning one's worship with the truth revealed by God's Word. This means that worship should be grounded in the reality of who God is, as revealed in Scripture, and in the redemptive work of Jesus Christ. By worshiping in spirit and truth, we ensure that our worship is both deeply personal and biblically sound, honouring God in a way that is pleasing and transformative for the worshiper.

Conclusion

A few years back, a newspaper headline read, "MISSING HYPHEN BLAMED IN ROCKET FAILURE" It was hard to believe that a small hyphen in a computer readout caused the destruction of a huge, powerful missile. On the day in question, a Venus space probe launch vehicle was boosted by an eighteen-million-dollar U.S. Atlas rocket was lost because a hyphen was missing from a computer equation. Richard Morrison, a NASA official, told the House Space Committee investigating the incident that the missing hyphen caused a mathematical miscue: "The hyphen gives a cue for the spacecraft to ignore the data

the computer feeds it until radar contact is once again restored. When this hyphen is left out, false information is fed into the spacecraft control systems. In this case, the computer was fed in hard left, nose down and the vehicle obeyed.' Who left out the hyphen? Morrison either did not know it or did not say it, but he speculated that it was the mistake of some senior official with advanced degrees and a Ph.D. in celestial navigation.

There is also an important hyphen that belongs to our lives. It doesn't seem like much, but without it, we can crash. That hyphen is worship. A time to pray, a time to read God's Word, and a time to listen to God's voice. Just a few minutes a day is all it takes to keep our lives going. Let us embrace a life of worship that is characterized by acknowledging God's holiness, abiding in God's presence, and aligning with God's word.

NATHANIEL, AN ENLIGHTENED PERSON: A REFLECTION BASED ON JOHN 1:44-51

Johnson Thomaskutty*

Introduction

The word ‘enlightenment’ can mean: “a state of awakened understanding, wisdom, and inner peace. It can also be described as the transcendence of suffering and desire to obtain spiritual liberation”; and in Buddhism, it is the final spiritual state in which everything is understood and there is no more suffering or desire. Enlightenment can also refer to the act of enlightening or the state of being enlightened. In Hinduism and Buddhism, enlightenment is the highest spiritual state that can be achieved. In the European context, the eighteenth century is considered as a period of enlightenment when many people began to emphasize the importance of science and reason, rather than religion and tradition. I would rather look at the traditional Eastern understanding of enlightenment. The basic denotation for *budh*—the Sanskrit root that gives us *buddha* (enlightened or awakened)—is to wake up or to recover consciousness.¹ As the Gospel of John is considered as “Gospel with the Indian Spirit,” let us look at how the character called Nathanael became a spiritually enlightened person in the presence of Jesus. From

* Rev. Dr. Johnson Thomaskutty is professor of the New Testament at the United Theological College, Bangalore.

1 Richard S. Cohen, *Beyond Enlightenment: Buddhism, religion, modernity* (London/New York: Routledge, 2006), 1.

the read passage (John 1:44-51), I would like to highlight five significant aspects for our reflection.

Nathanael was Called to Follow Jesus (vv. 44-45)

In v. 43, we see that “Finding Philip, Jesus said to him ‘Follow me.’” The Greek word used is *heuriskei*, not *blepei*. That means, it was not an accidental finding; but finding after a long search. The well-known Greek expression *Eureka* is an interjection attributed to the ancient Greek mathematician and inventor Archimedes. It is used to celebrate a discovery or invention. Just as Jesus found Philip after a long search, now Philip finds Nathanael after a long search. Both Jesus and Philip exclaim *Eureka* and celebrate what they found out after their search. Philip finds (the expression *heuriskei* is used in v. 45) Nathanael and he speaks unto him: “We have found the one Moses wrote about in the Law, and about whom the prophets also wrote.” The expression *heurēkamen* [we have found] reveals that Philip and his friends were in search of the Scriptures that describe the Messiah. The reference to Torah and Prophets indicates that Jesus’s coming reflects the fulfilment of the Scriptures. An Asian reader can understand Jesus even as the fulfilment of Hinduism as Farquhar considered him as the *Crown of Hinduism*. It is made clear that just as Jesus was in search of people, the people were in search of the Messiah.

Then Philip tells Nathanael: “Come and See.” According to Buddhist traditions, Buddha came to a certain village and told the villagers in Pali language “EhiPassiko” (Sanskrit, “Ehipaśyika”), which means “come and see for yourself” or “come and meditate with me.” This was Buddha’s invitation to the villagers to come and taste his words. Jesus tells the followers to “come and see”; in 1:39a, Jesus tells Andrew and the unknown disciple to “come and see”; and the Johannine community would have used the same expression as Philip tells the same to Nathanael in v. 46b. Not only Philip’s personal revelations and witnesses but also his witness to the Law of Moses and the Prophetical writings

about Jesus convinced Nathanael that Jesus was the Messiah. Philip has a special interest in finding Nathanael and calls him to follow Jesus. Both Philip and Nathanael came to an experience of *Eureka*.

Nathanael begins his journey of faith by asking a genuine question (v. 46)

Nathanael asks Philip: “Can anything good come from Nazareth?” As a Jew, Nathanael was aware that Messiah is not from Nazareth. Nathanael’s question to Philip in v. 46 (i.e., “Nazareth! Can anything good come from there?”) can be considered either as a commonly accepted proverbial statement or as a sarcastic statement concerning the impossibility of Messiah’s coming from Nazareth. It indicates that God works in nothingness and in hopeless situations of human life. Until recently, the Westerners posed a continuous question: “Can anything good come out of Indian and in the Asian realities?” Yes, Indian spirituality, Indian church growth, and Indian theology are the highlights of our times. Nathanael’s question is a significant alter call in the contemporary context as we stand in the crossroads of exegesis, hermeneutics and interpretation. People may comment about you: “Can anything good come out from this man or woman?” But God can bring something good out of our nothingness and difficult situations in life. Nathanael question “Can anything good come from Nazareth?” is the starting point of his enlightenment. In the Fourth Gospel, Thomas was enlightened when he was interrogative and sceptical in his spiritual journey and theological articulations (John 11:16; 14:5; 20:24-28; 21:2). Hence, he was able to come out with his enlightened utterance “My Lord and my God” (20:28). As Nathanael and Thomas are interrogative and sceptical in their spiritual journey, we are supposed to be interrogative and sceptical in our spiritual journey.

Nathanael is recognized as a 'True Israelite' (v. 47)

When Jesus saw Nathanael approaching, he said of him: "Here is a True Israelite, in whom there is nothing false." If Nathanael is recognized as a true Israelite, the implied meaning is that there are false Israelites too. Jacob in the Old Testament as the first Israel was a deceitful man who had treacherously stolen his own brother's blessings (Gen 27:35). Jacob was also called "holder of the heel" (Gen 27:36). In his birth, he was holding the heel of his brother. As a deceitful man by birth itself, he was called the "First Israel." But in the case of Nathanael, Jesus addresses him as a True Israelite. Jesus was searching for a new, true Israelite. In Nathanael, Jesus could find a new, true, ideal, perfect Israel. Jesus searches in us the True Israel; not a deceitful one as the old Israel.

We need to prove our truthfulness, genuine nature, transparency, and ideal character before Jesus. As we live in a context in which the *Hindutva* ideologists discriminate between the "true Indians" and the "spurious Indians" on the basis of their religious identity, Jesus discriminates people on the basis of their righteousness, believing nature, searching and finding the truth of God, and the experience of divine *Eureka*. Truthfulness is more valid in the presence of God far more than any other aspects.

Nathanael acknowledges Jesus as the 'King of Israel' (vv. 48-49)

Nathanael was amazed because a strange person praises him highly. He asks Jesus: "How do you know me?" Jesus replied: "I saw you while you were still under the fig tree before Philip called you." Jesus found Nathanael even before Philip found him. It demonstrates that Jesus's eyes were gazing upon him. Jewish men choose the shadow under fig trees to sit and study the scripture. As a devout Jewish man, Nathanael would have

studied the scripture under the shadow of fig trees. Now Nathanael got enough evidence that Jesus was indeed watching him. Nathanael's phenomenal utterance is: "Rabbi, you are the Son of God, you are the King of Israel." When Jesus accepts Nathanael as a "True Israelite," Nathanael accepts Jesus as the "King of Israel." This is what Jesus expects in this world: 'Jesus as the King of Israel and the True Israelites under his reign just like Nathanael-type people.' Indians can relate Nathanael in the following ways: his posture of sitting under the fig tree is reminiscent to the posture of Gautama Buddha who sat under a bodhi tree (a sacred fig or *figus religiosa*); Nathanael's understanding of Jesus as "Rabbi" corresponds with the *guru-shishya* traditions in the Indian religions; his realization that Jesus is "the Son of God and the King of Israel" in several ways similar to the enlightenment of Buddha; and if Nathanael is proved to be Bartholomew, he was connected to the Kalyan (Mumbai) tradition in the Indian context. A "New Israel" national concept is brainstormed and visualized here in which Jesus is the King and Nathanael-type people are the subjects. The narrator brings to the foreground the idea of "New Israel" in an innovative way: while Jacob was deceitful, Nathanael is without deceit (Gen 25:19-34; 27:1-41; v. 47b); and while Jacob visualized a ladder from heaven, Nathanael shall visualize an ascending and descending Son of Man figure (Gen 28:10-12; v. 51).

Nathanael is promised to see greater things (vv. 50-51)

In v. 50, Jesus says: "You believe because I told you I saw you under the fig tree. You shall see greater things than these." What greater things Nathanael is going to see?": first, he shall see an open heaven; and second, he shall see angels of God ascending and descending upon the Son of Man. It is similar to the experience of Jacob in Bethel. Jacob's vision of the ladder is stated in Gen 28:12. There is a transfer from deceitful Israel's experience in the Book of Genesis to True Israel in the Gospel of John. The True

Israel's association with the King of Israel is stated convincingly here. Though both the Old Israel and the True Israel saw the visions of angelic descending and ascending, one saw it with his deceitful mind whereas the other saw it in his truthfulness. Here, Nathanael is foregrounded as an enlightened person as he appears another time in John 21:2. He was one among the seven disciples in 21:1-2 who witnessed the resurrected Jesus and formed the nucleus of the church in the early Christian context.

Concluding Remarks

The story of Nathanael and the encounter of Jesus with him reveal that Jesus as the enlightened Son of God enlightened Nathanael as a True Israelite. The *Eureka* experience of Nathanael strengthened him to be a follower of Jesus Christ and a person of unique traits. The interrogative and sceptical mindset of Nathanael enabled him to understand the Messianic truths for the glory of God. As a true Israel, he was demonstrating his enlightened position and that was declared by Jesus the King of Israel. His search in the Scriptures, the posture of meditation under the fig tree, and the declaration that Jesus us "Rabbi, Son of God, and King of Israel" enlightened him to be a Buddha of Jesus. As an enlightened person, he was promised to see greater things, witnessed the resurrected Jesus, and formed the nucleus of the *ekklēsia* of God. In the contemporary Indian context, let us be enlightened by the wisdom of God to be transformers of the ecclesiastical structures and systems, liberators of the socially and religiously ostracized communities, and people who utilize their responsible freedom to elevate the vulnerable communities. May God guide us to be enlightened and enlightening people in the contemporary context!

SERMON ON THE MOUNT AS A KEY TO UNDERSTANDING JESUS' SOCIAL TEACHINGS AND SOCIAL JUSTICE AS A CHRISTIAN DUTY

Jeeva Kumar Ravela*

Introduction

The Sermon on the Mount is the best-known part of teachings of Jesus, presenting a message that persuades one to learn how to live a responsible social and spiritual life. Through this teaching Jesus enables his followers to live a model life in a world of conflicts. The Sermon on the Mount teaches Christian value systems, ethical standards, and a proper religious devotion. It accentuates appropriate ways that faith communities need to adopt in their journey of faith. It drives one to hold on to unique ambitions that respect life, and improve network of relationships among human communities irrespective of caste, class, and creed. This sermon not only teaches moral values to humanity but also reinterprets Jewish Torah in terms of its revitalization for welfare of the people especially as those who are marginalized in the society. Through this sermon Jesus expresses that his disciples must live an exemplary life. The teachings are intended

* Rev. Dr. Jeeva Kumar Ravela is Professor of the Old Testament at UTC, Bangalore.

to instruct a human life according to divine rule.¹ The sermon has a closely interwoven structure; it is meant to express Jesus' teachings of ethics. It emphasizes profound moral teachings and spiritual insights. Scholars considered the sermon on the Mount as a kind of parental catechism or Didache that constituted a most comprehensive pattern for Christian living in the teachings of New Testament.² This essay attempts to understand the social concern that was revealed in the message of Jesus from the Sermon on the Mount. In addition, the task is to discern the sermon with a concern of social justice that strive to establish an impetus for a meaningful Christian living in the contemporary society.

Socio-Cultural World of the Gospel of Mathew

Matthew formulates an ethical demarcation rather than a ritual demarcation of Judaism. Scholars argue that Matthew represents the first century C.E. Jewish community, which witnessed Jesus' movement of invigorating the teachings of Torah from a social and ethical dimension. The first century Jewish community experienced the dominance of Judaism and its imposition of legal teachings. Talbert maintains that Mathew's encounter of Judaism informs a new Christian Judaism that desires to propose a Christianity in the light of authority of Judaism.³ He acknowledges that Matthew's community had the thought of a Judaism, which is reformed and reshaped in light of Jesus' teachings. In this way Matthew's gospel is also a Judaism in which he presumes reformation of Judaism and its values. Matthew tries to bring out the perfection and fulfilment of Judaism amidst of various sects (Samaritanism, Pharisaism, early Christianity,

1 John R W Stott, *The Message of the Sermon on the Mount*, (Leicester: Inter-Varsity Press, 1984), 15ff.

2 Greenwood David, "Moral Obligations in the Sermon on the Mount" *Theological Studies* 31/2 (1970), 302.

3 C. H Talbert, *Reading the Sermon on the Mount: Character Formation and Ethical Decision making in Matthew 5-7*, (Michigan: Baker Academic, 2006), 6.

Essenism, apocalyptic Judaism and others), that struggle for their own existence in his gospel. Though there are many arguments with regard to Matthew's possession of gospel traditions, it is accepted that Matthew is writing the gospel from Jewish perspective struggling within Judaism for legitimacy.⁴ However Matthew, in his gospel focuses a synthesis of Jewish-Christian and Gentile-Christian traditions to moderate his fellow Jews towards a true Christian life. Mathew emphasizes stipulations of Torah and relates them to daily social life of the people, and thus, commits to uphold unique message of Jesus in his gospel.

R. T. France holds an opinion that Mathews' portrayal of community is faithful to its scriptural heritage, and it is open to new directions demanded by Jesus' proclamation of the values of kingdom of heaven.⁵ Matthew proclaims the rule of a Jewish king, who comes from the east and replaces the rule of Romans.⁶ Mathews combines Jewish messianic expectations with non-Jewish hopes as embodied in the arrival of magicians from the east (Matt 2:1ff). He radically redefines messiahship. A Militant messiah is replaced by a peace-making king, who rules the world by his teachings. The Old Testament scriptures affirms that establishment of a just society is responsibility of king (2 Sam 8:15; 1 K 10:9; Jer 22:3, 15; 23:5; 33:15; Ezek 45:9).⁷ It firmly emphasizes that earthly king is responsible to establish justice in society. Presumably, when Matthew views Jesus as a King, he intends to depict Jesus as the king, who establishes social justice on the earth, and commands his people to be part of this mission of establishing social justice. A prevailing notion of justice emphasizes equality, dignity, security and fair treatment to all

4 C. H. Talbert, *Reading the Sermon on the Mount*, 5.

5 R.T. France, "The Gospel of Matthew" *The New International Commentary on the New Testament*, (Michigan: Wm B Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2007), 17ff.

6 G. Theissen, *The New Testament: History, Literature, Religion*, Trans by J Bowden (London: T&T Clark, 2003), 121.

7 Moshe Weinfeld, *Social Justice in Ancient Israel and in Ancient near East*, (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1995) 45.

humans in a society. One can view that the Sermon on the Mount is the set of directions of Jesus to the Christian community that establishing social justice is a socio-spiritual responsibility. It eventually realizes the kingdom of God in the world of strife and sorrow.

Sermon on the Mount - Social Concerns of Jesus

The Sermon on the Mount, a collection of radical commands and absolute sayings, is surely one of the most central messages of the New Testament. Its implications to social concerns are vast. It clearly portrays social, religious and ethical commitments of Jesus that the early church learned and practiced. The sermon is fairly systematic, covering main areas of life of the people of God. It is neither purely arbitrary nor exhaustive, but a series of pointers illustrated by focal instances.⁸ The sermon is primarily concerned with the realization of one's humanity. How such realization is accomplished is explained in clear, extremely by concise terms. The central ethical demand of Jesus is resistance and love of enemies.⁹ Human intuition to possess a sense of generosity and mercy in every respect of life are proper responses to divine generosity and mercy.¹⁰ In the words of R. H. Mounce, 'Sermon on the Mount is the loftiest ideal for human conduct ever conceived'.¹¹ The eschatological interpretation of the Sermon on the Mount enables us to understand its radical and absolute demands. Indeed, faith communities are to be aware of the relationships between God and their fellow

8 Benedict T. Viviano, "The Gospel According to Mathew" *The New Jerome Bible Commentary*, ed by Raymond E. Brown, Joseph A. Fitzmayer and Ronald E. Murphy, (Bangalore: Theological Publications in India, 1992), 640.

9 Lisa Sowle Cahill, "The Ethical Interpretation of the Sermon on the Mount," *Interpretation* 41, no. 2 (1987): 145.

10 Hans Dieter Betz, "Sermon on the Mount / Plain", *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*, Vol-V, ed by David Noel Freedman. (New York: Doubleday, 1992),

11 R. H. Mounce, "Sermon on the Mount". *The International Standard Bible Encyclopedia*, ed by Geoffrey W. Bromiley (Grand Rapids, Michigan: W. B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1915), 411.

humans. The Sermon on the Mount enables us to look at the social concerns and develops an ethical conscious. The following is a short description of what the sermon on the mount wants the contemporary faith communities to learn and fulfil in their faith lives.

Wider Relationship and Prompt Action

Through the 'Sermon on the Mount' Jesus demands a new web of relationships. It portrays a new relationship to God as Father (sic), which is epitomized and made possible in and through Jesus. Jesus' expression of Fatherhood reveals divine intense character that desires to relate divine self with men and women in the world. Jesus wishes to promote a new kind of human world through the sermon.¹² Jesus emphasizes that human relationships must be established based on kith and kin values which is the desire of Father in the heaven. As father (sic), God wants every human to live in a significant relationship with one another as brothers and sisters. It is the will of God that intends to inaugurate the kingdom of God through the teachings of Jesus Christ. The quality of one's life in the Kingdom of God must be expressed not with mere inner emotions or mystical experiences, but pre-eminently with a social spirit that should bring all human kind in one accord.

The idea of brotherhood is the rule of life in the new humanity that Jesus talks about in the sermon. Those who hear Jesus' teachings become his disciples, and they are the children of God, and thus, they too know God as Father (5: 45). They form a new family, and describe brotherhood as its basic premise, which declares them as the children of God, and the disciples of Jesus, a community of saints (16: 18; 23: 8; 28: 10).¹³ The Fatherhood

12 Frederick Carl Eiselen, Edwin Lewis, and David G. Downey, eds., *The Abingdon Bible Commentary* (New York: Doubleday, 1957), 912.

13 Jack Dean Kingsbury, "The Place, Structure and Meaning of the Sermon on the Mount within Mathew," *Interpretation* 41, no. 2 (1987).137.

of God and universal brotherhood of human beings transform individuals and communities, so that, like God, they can look even on enemies selflessly, which makes them doers of the will of God. Here love is the binding factor. It is defined in Mathew's gospel as a way of acting, not as an emotion. Love is action that places other's best interests forward rather than one's desire. The Lord's Prayer clearly affirms this oneness and universality. It is our attitude towards others which will determine God's attitude of judgment or forgiveness towards us. The 'golden rule' in 7: 2 urges disciple to identify with one another to perceive other's concrete need as though it were the need of disciples. Further, disciples are required to act for others as though the other were disciple self. If one perceives other as alien, and approaches him/her in terms of gender, race, national, and class, it is certainly impossible to practice what Jesus teaches. One must presuppose that the divisions and barriers have ceased to exist, along with the institutions which support and feed on them. Eventually such relations motivate one another to find a society where there is no social inequality and disparity among the humans. Ultimately it directs people to promote social values that they learn in the course of growing relationship with God as well as with their fellow human beings.

Social Concerns of the Kingdom values

A key theme of the Sermon is the 'Kingdom of God'. The Kingdom of God means rule or reign of God. Here, the conception of the Kingdom of God is not political or national. In the beatitudes and elsewhere Jesus speaks of some little ones for whom the kingdom of heaven belongs. Those blessed with the Kingdom are 'poor in spirit' (5: 3), meek (5:5), merciful (5:7), pure in heart (5: 8), and peacemakers (5:9). Those who are hunger and thirst for righteousness, and those who are ready to be persecuted by those who judge by power and status, and those who suffer because of burden of the law of the scribes and Pharisees inherit

blessings of the kingdom of God. Jesus promises the Kingdom of God to the socially and economically disadvantaged groups, oppressed communities and to those live without hope.¹⁴ God's rule requires identification with the oppressed, mutual solidarity, liberation from fear, and practice of justice that enhances human welfare.

The Kingdom of God assures that sufferings of hunger, and struggles of destitute will turn into promises of hope and comfort. Perhaps, the marginal members of Jewish society, who suffer day after day from the futility of all their exertion, hope is assured that despite suffering and struggles.¹⁵ Jesus challenges status quo, and destabilizes secular and cultural norms of traditional Roman society. Commentators believe that the Sermon on the mount is a manifesto that Jesus prepared for his initial outline, making himself reaching out to the poor, the hungry, the meek, the oppressed and the persecuted.¹⁶ The kingdom of God is replete with values of social justice, equality, unselfishness and the worth of humanity. Thus, the values of kingdom of God encourage the followers of Jesus to have knowledge of social concern, and it leads to establish justice in a society.

Social dimension of the Righteousness of Disciples

The Sermon on the Mount affirms a call to disciples to involve in social inclusion and merciful action. The reign of God brings socio-political transformation that capitalizes a new human community to do good. It is asserting to state that the theme of the Sermon on the Mount is "greater righteousness". "The greater righteousness" is a style of life that intends to depict

14 Warren S. Kissinger, *The Sermon on the Mount: A History of Interpretation and Bibliography* (New Jersey: The Scarecrow Press and the American Library Association, 1975), 89.

15 Pinchas Lapide, *The Sermon on the Mount: Utopia or Program for Action* (New York: Orbis Book, 1986), 27.

16 William R. Farmer, 'Mathew' *The International Bible Commentary* (Bangalore: Theological Publications in India, 1998), 1336.

a mark of disciples of Jesus. Here Jesus, the son of God, calls people to follow him, which is to say that he summons them to enter and to live in the sphere of God's eschatological Kingdom. Righteousness in God's eyes is not purity and law-abidingness, but mercifulness effective in compassionate action. The 'greater righteousness' is an indication of a life with equality that makes up the church. It is the love towards God and love towards neighbour constitute greater righteousness.¹⁷ God has acted to establish a new relationship between Godself and humanity, offering the life of Jesus as a basis for a new relationship. Jesus' teachings express his intended relationship with the world, and demand the greater 'righteousness'. (5:21-7:12). Out of his relationship emerges a conduct that stems from a 'wholeness' (4:48) in one's relationship to God and others.¹⁸ By having such righteous relationship with God, believers cannot restrict themselves within religious living but to be active agents in social affairs. They perform the values that they learn from their righteous fellowship with God to ensure a sociable living for wellbeing of human communities.

Contemporary Context

We are living in a world of pluralism. Caste, colour, religion and region separate one another in our society. Jesus' social concern expressed in the Sermon on the Mount is of paramount significance to comprehend oneness while living diverse in its existence. Affirmation of the Fatherhood of God and universal brotherhood of humankind call us to come together irrespective of dividing factors. The real challenge is for a new relationship and action in the light of the Kingdom values. The Sermon on Mount calls us for solidarity with the little ones of the community. In a context of religious violence and fanaticism Sermon sets a

17 Kingsbury. "The Place, Structure and Meaning of the Sermon on the Mount within Mathew," 136.

18 Robert A. Guelich, *The Sermon on the Mount: A Foundation for Understanding* (Texas: Word Books Publishers, 1982), 38.

different approach of resistance to violence and promotes peace-making. The demand for a greater righteousness is the real challenge for a new relationship based on the will of God. The promises envisage a divinely effected transformation that would overturn human made barriers, structures and demarcations into spaces of accepting one another as the children of God.

Conclusion

No other short section of the Bible has been more prominent in theological discussion, and ministry of the church than the Sermon on the Mount. Even in our modern, secular societies the Sermon's influence continues. One can assert that the sermon contains vibrant social and ethical teachings for all people. It attracts many thinkers and freedom fighters to declare it as the world's finest collection of social and ethical teachings. The Sermon on the Mount demands for a higher quality of life that considers righteous living and just actions are significant factors for any faith community to learn and practice. The sermon is not a programme for social reform but a set of ethics directed to those who are entering into the Kingdom of God. It is not a blueprint for establishing Utopian community but the description of transformation that one must consider to attain. It is neither an impractical ideal nor a fully attainable possibility, but it grants directions and descriptions to realize the kingdom of God that is open for everyone. To conclude, the Sermon on the Mount is divine transcendence in the form of ethics that human communities must understand for a glorious living in the world.

11

PROPHETIC IMAGINATION OF THE SELF: REFLECTION FROM ISAIAH 11: 1-5; MATTHEW 8: 28-34

Eyingbeni Humtsoe-Nienu*

Introduction

Drawing your attention to the Gospel text, let me you a question: how many demons live inside of you? What are of all the social evils that we condemn? Are they in one way or the other nestled deep within us so that we become major tormentors of people we speak to defend and respect? Are we an obstacle to the liberating work of our Savior Jesus Christ in overthrowing the evils of our time? Are you willing, like the two demoniacs in the Gospel text, for willing for the demons to be cast out of you so that the world will want to see and seek Jesus? Or are you like city dwellers who rejected the working of Christ, asking him to leave them in their evil conditions because there is plenty of worldly gains at stake? The “self” can be instrumental in the formation of either a prophetic or destructive imagination.

Based on Isaiah 11: 1-5, let us understand the importance of individuality in transforming the world around and beyond us. Furthermore, who is better person than the Messiah, - the ultimate prophet to inform our prophetic imagination of ourselves? The prophet Isaiah presents an image of Jesus that provides for us

* Dr. Eyingbeni Humtsoe-Nienu is professor of Theology at the United Theological College, Bangalore. Formerly she served as the Principal of Baptist Theological College, Pfutsero, Nagaland, and also taught at Clark Theological College, Mokokchung, Eastern Theological College, Jorhat, and Academy of Integrated Christian Studies, Aizawl.

thought patterns and action plans - a blueprint – if we may say so – of what a prophetic imagination of the ‘self’ entails.

The self must seek greater power beyond oneself (Isaiah 11:1&2)

The spirit of the Lord shall rest upon him, the spirit of wisdom and understanding, the spirit of counsel, and might, the spirit of knowledge. Is it not a wonder that the promised Messiah, the Anointed One of God – the Word and son of God - will receive empowering to perform God’s work? Jesus’ Baptism and the Pentecost are manifestations of how much we need God’s empowering to prophetically imagine ourselves in the light of the Gospel’s demands. More so when we realize that we are just an entity in the vast ocean of humankind. All changes – for better or worse – swing from individuals. In almost all cases, individual ignites a spark of revolutions.

Our world today is a bit paradoxical. There seems to be a growing awareness of the human need for others and, at the same time, usually, no deliberate effort to go beyond ourselves and reach out for help. Perhaps, this is a problem of trust deficit and a feeling of absolute independence. In our younger days, when smartphones were not invented, we needed people to take our own photos. We would stop anyone and would happily click a picture. If you were lucky, you would get good shots, but if the stranger photographer wasn’t skillful, you would have lost a few precious reels. Today, you were to give your iPhone to a stranger to click on a photo; there would also be suspicion that the person may just run away with it! So, you dare not trust strangers with your belongings! Even for such mundane things, you need a divine sense to judge human character.

Prophetic imagination can simply be reduced to daydreaming without the Spirit of God, who guides, educates, and counsels our engagement with the affairs of the world. In seeking greater

power beyond the self, i.e., the Spirit of God, we, as human beings, admit our frailty and simultaneously declare that we are in divine business. Back to the Gospel text: When the two demoniacs saw Jesus Christ, they shouted at him, saying, "What have you to do with us, Son of God!" Every time we feel like being full of ourselves, remember that is the demons inside of us that question our need for God and his Spirit. Our prophetic imagination should start with us admitting that God has everything to do with us and the world. Furthermore, only with his empowerment can we do anything transformative in his name.

The self must not be controlled by people's opinion (Isaiah 11: 3)

His delight shall be in the fear of the Lord. He shall not judge by what his eyes see or decide by what his ears hear. What Isaiah is projecting is that Jesus will not be a gossipmonger. He will not simply sit and chat all day long reporting what he has seen or heard about one thing or another when the world around him is dying in unrighteousness. Moreover, he will not care what the people will talk about him behind his back or insult him on his face. He would have the clarity of his call and mission and so would be unfazed by whatever the world said about him or did to him, even if it meant being condemned as a criminal and crucified.

In the general Indian context, we fear people and their opinions more than anything. Many decisions and behaviors are guided by the saying, "log kya kehenge?" (what will the people say?). Apparently, this is also the driving force of today's hypocritical church and society. We, as individuals and as a collective church, either go silent when needing to bring justice to those who have been wronged or become very loud when it benefits us personally. Conversely, we are quick to speak of systemic corruption, but when that same system works in our individual

favors, then our tongues are suddenly tied. This reality confirms that those claiming to be ministers of God are most afraid of losing the favour of humans than of God's (Catholic theology outrightly calls this - "sin of human respect!").

Our quest to be in the good books of those who can give us something in return is turning us and, as a consequence, our churches into tributary societies that thrive on the principle of 'you scratch my back and I'll scratch yours'. Where, then, is the fear of the Lord? Where is the divine endowment that enables us to transcend our narrow sensibilities? To delight in the fear of the Lord is to be joyful in making God's presence and work evident in the world through us. This happens when the least, last, and the lost in our households and communities are treated as God's children just as any person we deem dignified or any individual who loves himself enough to know that we are God's handiwork. Prophetic imagination of the self should involve prioritizing the fear of God more than people - no matter how powerful, wealthy, or intimidating they might be- knowing that God is Sovereign and building his reign on earth is the supreme goal of Christian life and ministry, which begins with the self.

The self must embody righteousness (Isaiah 11: 4-5a)

(But) with righteousness he shall judge the poor and decide equity for the meek of the earth; he shall strike the earth with the rod of his mouth, and with the breath of his lips he shall kill the wicked. Righteousness is the belt around his waist. Righteousness involves doing right according to God's standards. That often means an intentional decision to see things from the opposite side of the dominant and the powerful, as Jesus did. If Jesus were to judge by human standards, he would have approved the conduct of the Jewish religious authorities, Pharisees, and Sadducees, and commending the powers and authorities of the Roman colonizers. But he did not! If we were to judge by our carnal sense of righteousness, we would be looking at the rich, the popular, the able-bodied, perfectly structured

people, mega churches and saying, “look how righteous they are!” “God is pleased with them!” That is what is happening in the war between Israel and Palestine. We look at the military power of Israel; they bomb and gas and shoot children, women, the elderly, the sick, and whatever and whoever comes in the way of their weapons, and we say, they are God’s chosen people! As it is, war should never have happened; it is an unnecessary evil. Moreover, when there’s unequal military power the mighty one is nothing but a bully. Israeli or pro-Israelism may not be willing to agree, but this war is a case of Goliath vs David. Only this time in modern history has the role of the Palestinians been reversed, and the outcome is sadly becoming disastrous for our proverbial David, the Palestinians. Are we looking at things from modern-day David or Goliath perspective?

Isaiah states that the promised Messiah will judge righteously. The Gospels witness how he judged. He saw the crookedness, the wickedness, the cruelty, the legalism, and the hypocrisy of those whom society deemed righteous, and they themselves claimed to be so. He judged their self-proclaimed righteousness with hyperbolic name-calling, such as the brood of vipers and whitewashed tombs, and labelled them as blind guides and fools. Is our imagination of righteousness only skin deep, or do we eat, drink, speak, do, and even die for righteousness’ sake (Cf., Matthew 5: 10)? Have we, like Jesus, embodied righteousness to the point that we can be sure that all our ways are just, as Deuteronomy 32:4 would say of God? Do we make it our duty as God’s ministers to peer into the outer appearances of our church, community, and nation and challenge the underlying sinful currents that make some people filthy rich and others dirt poor? Does it burn within you to know that the wealth of some is at the expense of life and the tears of others, like when companies take land and resources from the poor it’s a matter of life and death – while for the company it is just another project in the long list of things to do and profits to make.

The commitment to do right by God is the belt that secures the garments of our time. As a garment/loin provides dignity to the king, our ideas of righteousness must cover the nakedness and by extension the shame, the dishonor, and loss of the vulnerable and exploited, and thereby restoring the intrinsic worth and rights of every being.

In closing, I want to ask again, 'are there demons living inside you?' A prophetic imagination can turn into prophetic action when the demons within an individual are first cast out to be annihilated. The self bears that image of God, and whatever cause we champion in God's name must first of all be actualized in the person. To do so, we need God's spirit to enable us, his approval over humans, and the embody of divine righteousness.

12

JESUS, THE PROPHET

Ben Das*

Introduction

Our understanding of Jesus is vivid. Each believer believes in Jesus and God according to their faith and experiences. We cannot deny the fact that Christians often misinterpret and misunderstand and Jesus. Some of these misconceptions came from other religions like Zoroastrianism, Judaism and Islam. Without realizing the difference in sources, some Christians interpret Christianity based on their own hearsay. Quran has so many references about Christians, Christianity and Jesus. Particularly Sura 3 and 19 have many references to Jesus. In the overall Quranic understanding, Jesus was a prophet, and a messenger.

Islam teaches that God has sent many prophets into the world. According to Islamic traditions, there are 24 lakh prophets among whom Adam was the first and Muhammad the last. They also believe that the six prophets (Adam, Noah, Abraham, Moses, Jesus and Muhammad) who are the heads of their dispensations are, given special titles. Muslims refer to them by different titles. Adam is known as Safiu'llah (the Chosen of God), Noah as Nabiu'llah (the Prophet of God), Abraham as Khalilu'llah (the Friend of God), Moses as Kalimu'llah (the One Who Speaks with God), Jesus as Kalimatu'llah (the Word of God), and Muhammad as Razulu'llah (the Messenger of God). Islamic theology classifies

* Rev. Dr. D. S. Ben Das is Associate Professor in the Department of Religions, & Interim PRO, UTC. This is the sermon preached in the Sunday Community Communion worship at UTC Chapel on 21 - 07 - 2024.

prophets into two categories, viz., *Nabi* and *Razul*. *Nabi* is the one who receives *Wahī* (the highest form of inspiration) but does, not necessarily deliver the message. *Razul* is considered as the Messenger or Apostle who not only receives *Wahī* (the highest form of inspiration), but is, also commanded to deliver it to the people. Islamic theology, thus, categorise Jesus as a *Razul*.

In Sura 3 āyāt 45, we see the beginning of a conversation between angels and Maryam, who gave birth to Jesus. In their conversation, in āyāts 48 and 49, angel says Maryam, “Allah will teach him the Book and Wisdom, the Torah and Bible (the Gospel), and appoint him a messenger to the children of Israel.” Considering Jesus as a prophet may not be acceptable for all Christians. However, there are a handful of references even in the Bible where Jesus was referred to as a prophet, and in Mark 6: 4, the title “prophet” was alluded to by Jesus himself. Therefore, rather than getting upset by Jesus being perceived as a prophet, we need to understand how Jesus was a prophet. Because we are called to follow Jesus, we have the responsibility to learn from Jesus, a prophet for many. Hence, let us briefly learn about the prophetic ministry of Jesus.

Contextualisation of God’s Message

When Angel was talking to Maryam about Jesus, he said that one of the messages of Jesus to the world would be that he would be in the world confirming the Torah (not to nullify it). Furthermore, He is in the world ‘to make lawful part of what was before forbidden to the world’ (Sura 3, āyāt 50b). This means that while confirming Torah, Jesus conveys a message that makes lawful things that were previously forbidden. This is the contextualization of Torah by Jesus. This is a duty all prophets have undertaken out God’s inspiration.

Referring to Lev. 19¹⁸ and Deut. 23⁶ where the Israelites were told not to take vengeance against one another, it is told: “You

shall never promote their welfare or their prosperity as long as you live," Jesus was reminding the crowd at the Sermon on the Mount in Mt. 5⁴³⁻⁴⁴, "You have heard that it was said, 'You shall love your neighbour and hate your enemy.' Then Jesus taught them: "But I say to you, Love your enemies and pray for those who persecute you." Here, we see the contextualization of the earlier teachings by Jesus.

There are so many examples of this kind in the Bible, in the teachings of Jesus, and those of the disciples and early church fathers. I shall cite another example from Ex. 23¹⁹ and 2 Tim. 2⁶. This is the contextualization of the teaching on the first fruit. During the time of Old Testament, and during the Before Common Era, the Israelites were taught the Torah (Ex. 23¹⁹) as follows: "The choicest of the first fruit of your ground you shall bring into the house of the Lord your God." After centuries, during the time of apostles, Paul wrote to Timothy in his second letter: "It is the farmer who does the work who ought to have the first share of the crops" (2 Tim. 2⁶). In the Old Testament, people were taught and urged to bring their first fruit to the house of God, whereas in the Epistle period, the early church taught and encouraged farmers to enjoy the first fruit.

This is Contextualization of the message, and this is what is told in Sura 3^{50b} about Jesus' duty. Jesus came to the world 'to make lawful part of what was before forbidden to the world.' By doing so, the Torah or the earlier teachings are not nullified but become relevant to changing life-situations.

Today, it is our duty to contextualize the Word of God. This does not mean that whatever teachings we had are to be taught in its contrary, but it means that whatever teachings are irrelevant today have to be replaced and made relevant with new perspectives and new meanings, considering the changing life realities. In no case contextualization contradict with the basic teachings of the Bible. With devotion and listening to God's

spirit, we can do it. Our writings, teachings, and sermons should contextualize the earlier teachings, and only then do, they have relevance today.

Being A Spokesperson for God

Another duty of a prophet is to be a Spokesperson for God. Jn. 6¹⁻¹⁴ is about the feeding of the five-thousand with 5 barley loaves and two fish. When the people saw the sign that he had done, they began to say, "This is indeed the prophet who is to come into the world" (Jn. 6¹⁴). The periscope ends with the reporting of Jesus' withdrawal from that place since he realized that people were about to take him by force to make him king (Jn. 6¹⁵). People wished him to be their king so that they would have enough food for their stomach but, Jesus withdrew himself since that was not his mission on earth. Then he continued his ministry, and when we reach the very next chapter, i.e., Jn. 7, we see Jesus attending the Festival of Booths (Jn. 7¹⁰⁻³¹). About the middle of the festival, Jesus went up into the temple and began to teach. On listening to him, Jews were astonished at it saying: "How does this man have such learning, when he has never been taught?" He said: "My teaching is not mine but his who sent me" (Jn. 7¹⁴⁻¹⁶).

Whatever Jesus taught in the world was not coming out of Jesus, the individual, but God was teaching the world through Jesus. In other words, Jesus' teachings were God's heart. His tongue was God's tongue. Jesus spoke on behalf God. He never spoke of anything of his own, as recorded in Jn. 8²⁸. His tongue was controlled by God; in other words, he never spoke anything that God did not want to speak to the world. Therefore, Jesus was a spokesperson for God in its fullest sense.

When we look into the work of the Old Testament prophets, we also see the same in their lives. God uses them as the mouthpiece of God to speak to the world, guide the world, teach the world, and warn the world. But when some of them started talking

about themselves for personal gain or for personal purposes, God turned against them. Balaam (Num. 22) and Hananiah (Jer. 28) are the best examples. When Balaam repented and surrendered to God, God continued using him; however, since Hananiah spoke in the name of God while he was not used by God, God punished him with capital punishment.

As spokespersons for God, prophets always speak truths as God inspires them. We must speak and teach the truth to God's people. The truth we realize through our theological learning must be shared with believers. For example, when we study the origins of communion, we realize the fact that the reason for using bread and wine has a cultural reason, not a faith reason, for Israelites. Bread and wine have a totally different connotation for Indians. But even after realizing the fact, the Indian church continues to use bread and wine as the elements for communion. This is the same case with some other Christian practices like baptism. As we realize the truth, we have the responsibility to teach it to the church today and to help the Church to come out of its mistakes.

Therefore, as the ones who are called by God for God's ministry, we have to allow God to use our tongue and we should not take God's name if God do not share any message with us for the people of God. Being for God, standing for God, speaking for God, and denying all temptations of personal gain and interests for God may bring pain to us through the world, but our actions will glorify God, and God will bless us and our future generations, as seen in the lives of the truthful prophets.

Guiding People of God

Another function Jesus performed as a prophet is to guide God's people. Jn. 1⁴³ - 5¹ narrates the conversation of Philip and Nathanael about Jesus. After receiving a call from Jesus, Philip went to Nathanael and told him: "We have found him about

whom Moses in the law and the prophets wrote, Jesus son of Joseph from Nazareth" (Jn. 1⁴⁵). While mentioning the Law of Moses in his conversation, Philip was referring to Deut. 18¹⁵, where it is written: "The Lord your God will raise up for you a prophet like me from among your own people; you shall heed such a prophet." The same is referred again in some other places like Acts. 3²²⁻²³.

As per the teaching of Moses, the Jews were awaiting the coming of a prophet like Moses to guide them, and they were willing to listen to him. But when Jesus came into the world to fulfil the words of Moses, Jews could not recognize him since they were expecting the prophet to arrive in a totally different social setting. Some people like Philip recognized Jesus as the one mentioned by Moses.

Our concern today is not about the issue of recognition but about Jesus' role, which Moses predicted. Moses assured the Israelites that the coming of a prophet like him would come, meaning that the prophet would guide them in their struggles and take them to the Promised Land in its eternal sense. This is the duty Jesus performed in his life as a prophet. Throughout his life, Jesus was trying to guide God's people who were in the slavery of sin to a life of liberation from sin. For that, he went to the streets where people gathered, attracted them by performing miracles, and at times, he had to encounter false teachers who were misleading them for their vested interests.

Although Moses urged God's people through his Law Book to listen to him, only a few could listen to him, and the majority rejected Jesus. When Jesus was teaching at Nazareth on a Sabbath day in the synagogue, many who heard him were astounded. They were amazed at the wisdom Jesus had, the power his words had, and the power his deeds had. But when they came to know about the identity of Jesus, the same people started offending Jesus saying, "Is not this the carpenter, the son of Mary and

brother of James and Simon?" Then Jesus said to them: "Prophets are not without honour, except in their hometown, and among their own kin, and in their own house" (Jn. 6¹⁻⁶). The feeding of the thousand was preceded by the teaching of Jesus which started when "he saw a great crowd; and he had compassion for them, because they were like sheep without a shepherd; and he began to teach them many things" (Mark 6³⁴). Jesus was aware of the institutionalised pattern of the Temple and the synagogue to teach the Law, but still Jesus realised that the needy are not taken care of by the systems. Then he started catering to the needs of the sheep, who had no shepherd, through his teachings and works. This satisfied many and also roused many enemies.

Dear sisters and brothers, we are now called the prophets for the world. But do not expect respect and acceptance if you are doing your duty truthfully; only expect rejection and offences as Jesus had to face in his prophetic mission in his times. The cross is the assurance that one can accomplish an effective prophetic mission, not by an outsider but always by one who must embrace the pain.

Conclusion

Ostad Elahi, a Persian musician, thinker, and jurist best known for his work in self-knowledge and existential meaning, told: "When you consider all saints and prophets as legitimate and no longer differentiate between religions, you have reached the stage of true mysticism." As I mentioned in the introduction of this sermon, Jesus is perceived differently by different people, not only in our times but, even in the time of Jesus. For some, Jesus was Messiah; for others he was the Son of God; for others, he was a miracle-doer, and for others, he was a prophet. As recorded in the Bible by different writers of different times and in the Quran by Muslims, we should look into Jesus as a prophet. A detailed study of his prophetic mission will help us equip ourselves for a meaningful and fruitful ministry in our lives. I conclude my reflection by quoting Wallace D. Wattles,

an American New Thought writer: “The prophets and seers and great men and women, past and present, were made great by what they perceived from God, not by what they were taught by humans.” May God use all of us as the prophets for God’s glory and blessing of the surrounding world us.

THE IMPACT OF RESTORATIVE JUSTICE ON THE WELFARE OF VICTIMS OF CRIMINAL FALSE ACCUSATION CASES: AN EXAMINATION OF LUKE 4:18-19

Praveen Kodyattil*

Introduction

Life is undeniably a divine bestowal; it is justifiable to strive for a complete and fulfilling existence, regardless of acknowledging this truth. Injustice occurs when individuals or systems infringe against someone's inherent right to experience the life bestowed upon them by God. Regrettably, the current legal system's constraints permit situations in which blameless individuals who contribute to society by paying taxes are subjected to trials and penalties for crimes they did not commit. Victims of criminal frame-up cases are deprived of their quality of life, even after being freed from jail or confinement. Restorative justice plays a significant role in addressing the injustices faced by victims of unlawful convictions. This study examines Luke 4:18-19 to extract the implications of restorative justice for the well-being of victims in criminal frame-up cases. Additionally, it uses insights from secular restorative justice projects.

* Fr. Praveen Kodyattil is a Priest of the Jacobite Syrian Orthodox Church in Kerala. He completed Master of Theology from UTC, Bangalore.

Kathleen Daly, a criminology and criminal justice professor, notes that there is no universally accepted definition of Restorative Justice.¹ She identifies this as a significant constraint of the Restorative Justice, which encompasses a collection of principles regarding justice that presupposes a magnanimous, compassionate, encouraging, and logical human nature. Restorative Justice encompasses three evolving models: mediation, circles, and conferencing. They evolved autonomously, and each had a distinct impact on the others. The fundamental process of restoration has extensive consequences for resolving conflicts and the reestablishment of relationships. Restorative justice defines crime as the transgression of individuals and interpersonal connections. Therefore, Restorative Justice incorporates the victim, offender, and community into a collaborative effort to find solutions that encourage restoration, reconciliation, and comfort. The retributive model of conventional justice relies on an adversarial approach that divides communities to determine guilt and impose punishment.² In contrast, the restorative model emphasises a communal approach to address the harms caused by crime and promote the offender's reintegration. Conventional justice is founded on the principles of individual rights, ensures legal fairness, and is limited to a single culture. Restorative justice, in contrast, is founded on the notion of obligations; it offers ethical justice, and is inclusive of multiple cultures.

Spiritual Foundations of Restorative Justice

Restorative justice fundamentally involves a profound spiritual process that results in a metamorphosis of individuals, circumstances, and organisations. Based on spiritual principles, it comprehensively addresses the needs of individuals to repair

- 1 Kathleen Daly, —The Limits of Restorative Justice, in *Handbook of Restorative Justice: A Global Perspective* (ed. Dennis Sullivan and Larry Tifft; London: Routledge, 2006), 134.
- 2 H. R. Bhardwaj, *Crime, Criminal Justice and Human Rights* (Delhi: Konark Publishers, 2001), 50.

their moral connections within society. It entails acknowledging justice not only in relation to legal processes involving opposing sides but, also in terms of restoring, mending, and achieving peace.³ Throughout history, there has been a strong correlation between the legal system and religious beliefs. In Israel, the Torah is the authoritative legal text that governs the lives of people. The distinction between secular and religious existence was minimal.⁴ The religious law exerts influence over the public and private morality of people. Nevertheless, religious faith alone does not ensure ethical behaviour. Religious beliefs can manifest as hostile and tyrannical in several ways. However, Armstrong suggested that the level of religion should be evaluated based on the extent to which it is demonstrated through acts of compassion. The essence of a religion's spirituality is not demonstrated by its belligerence, but rather through its capacity to manifest love, compassion, and justice. Essentially, all religious beliefs are dedicated to upholding a covenant that promotes justice, peace, and preservation of the natural world. First, they advocate for accountability, repentance, or a complete shift in direction, forgiveness, compassion, and reconciliation.⁵ These are the characteristics of a person who works in the field of restorative justice. Frequently, religions have forsaken their initial objectives and align themselves with prevailing authorities, advocating strict adherence to rules and stability.

Restorative Justice in Old Testament

Old Testament justice became imperative when violence was mentioned in historical annals. The initial alienation occurred

3 Christ Wood, *The End of Punishment: Christian Perspectives on the Crisis in Criminal Justice* (Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh, 1991), 81.

4 Joel B. Green, *The Theology of the Gospel of Luke* (Cambridge: Cambridge University, 1995), 80–82.

5 Joel B. Green, *The Theology of the Gospel of Luke...*, 97.

in Genesis 4 when Cain committed the act of fratricide by murdering Abel. Further, it took place when people engaged in acts of violence (vv. 9-11) and when individuals sought to ascend to heaven (v. 11). God initially responded with a significant act of punishment, unleashing a flood because of tremendous sadness. However, God then remembered Noah and summoned humanity, making a solemn promise to never again cause their destruction in this manner. Genesis 12 depicts the call of Abraham as a means of disseminating God's bounty to numerous others. Ted Grimsrud refers to this approach as "God's healing strategy." In response to human estrangement and injustice, God selected a tiny society dedicated to peace with, the intention of spreading this peace throughout all creation. The remainder of the Bible is a re-enactment of this narrative. Justice serves the purpose of preserving life and, is an integral component of an established structure. Justice is frequently associated with themes such as "unwavering affection," "empathy," "generosity," "harmony," and "deliverance."⁶ Justice does not show leniency towards wickedness, but instead eradicates wickedness. God's justice specifically focuses on the most disadvantaged individuals in society. Justice is the state of being complete and harmonious, where all individuals within a community maintain proper and fair connections with each other and with God. Thus, in Hebrew tradition, the concept of divine justice is predominantly focused on restoring or rebuilding, as it involves God's redemptive intervention to restore harmony and rectify any wrongdoing.

Restorative Justice in the New Testament

While the Old Testament emphasises righteousness and justice by adhering to the Law, the New Testament places greater emphasis on righteousness and justice through faith in the Messiah, repentance from sin, and good living. According to

⁶ Ted Grimsrud and Howard Zehr, *Rethinking God, Justice, and Treatment of Offenders*, JOR 35 (2002): 259-285

John Haughey, the life of Jesus and, his career as witnessed by the gospels serve as manifestations of divine justice.⁷ Jesus' life, death, and resurrection are integral part of God's restorative justice. This event involves rectifying injustices on earth, fostering God's closer relationship with humankind, and creating a new community that lives a transformed life. This transformed life includes showing radical forgiveness to offenders and practicing non-violence towards opponents. Paul intentionally uses the categories and terminologies of justice and justice-making to elucidate God's achievements in Christ. Both Jews and Gentiles are equally culpable for their transgressions. Therefore, God's eschatological justice is manifested through the death and resurrection of Jesus. Through the redemptive work of Christ, the covenantal relationship is restored and accessible to anyone who responds with faith. Therefore, Justification by faith is an expression of restorative justice.⁸ Throughout the New Testament, there is a recurring theme that emphasises the superiority of mercy over judgement. This concept, as stated in James 2:13, serves as a way to uphold justice by restoring proper relationships. Therefore, restorative justice is not a mere subjective assumption; rather, it objectively originates from God and is a divine attribute.

Significance of Luke 4:18-21

Luke 4:18-21 serves as the foundational element for the entire account of Jesus' ministry in the Gospel of Luke. The passage's rhetorical structure guides the intended reader to comprehend the expansion of Jesus' ministry to Gentiles, a key theme in Acts. However, chronologically, Luke maintains a method that

⁷ John C. Haughey, Jesus as the Justice of God, in *The Faith That Does Justice: Examining the Christian Sources for Social Change* (ed. John C. Haughey; Eugene: Wipf & Stock, 1977), 264–90.

⁸ Patrick E. Spenser, *Rhetorical Texture and Narrative Trajectories of the Lukan Galilean Ministry Speeches: Hermeneutical Appropriation by Authorial Readers of Luke-Acts* (London: T&T Clark, 2007), 135.

prioritises Jews.⁹ The speech's rhetorical texture convinces the presumed reader about Jesus' identity. Luke tactically uses the passage to insinuate Jesus' identity and elucidate his function. Jesus is consecrated by the Spirit (3:22) according to the prophecy of Isaiah, who promises and achieves emancipation and justice (salvation) for all humanity by surpassing cultural norms. The concept of salvation is depicted in Jubilee imagery. The account describes Jesus' prophetic anointing (v. 18ff), his mission defined as evangelisation (v. 18,43), the content of his mission as the good news (v. 18c) of the Kingdom of God (v. 43), the importance of declaring this urgently (v. 43), and the realisation that it is currently happening (v. 21).

Jesus confirms Restorative Justice

The reference to "The Spirit of the Lord is upon me" in Luke 3:22 is reminiscent of the moment when the Spirit descended upon Jesus and, bestowed upon him the power to carry out his mission (4:14). This power enhances Jesus' ability to exert dynamic influence on the pursuit of restorative justice through his teachings and actions.¹⁰ He advocates for restorative justice with a sense of liberation, courage, and autonomy. Nevertheless, the quotation highlights God's assignment to Jesus for a specific purpose. This emphasises Jesus' prophetic role as the messenger of the "good news," particularly to those who are impoverished, imprisoned, visually impaired, and oppressed. Evangelist Luke places a greater emphasis on Jesus' function as a prophet more than his counterparts. He specifically associates this prophetic activity with Jesus' teachings and martyrdom, as shown in passages 4:23, 2:39, 13:33-34, and 24:19.

⁹ Joel B. Green, *The Theology of the Gospel of Luke...*, 99.

¹⁰ James Massey, *The Gospel According to Luke* (New Delhi: Centre for Dalit/Subaltern Studies, 2007), 72.

Ministry of release: A proclamation of restoration

The phrases “to proclaim release for captives” and “to send the oppressed in release” in verse 18 should be interpreted in conjunction with their parallelism. This arrangement of Lukan’s work highlights prominent placement of the recurring phrases ‘me’ and ‘release’ thereby capturing the attention of the audience. The Jubilee release cannot be interpreted solely as a spiritual act of forgiving sins, nor can it be reduced to a mere social transformation. It includes the process of restoring one’s spiritual well-being, transforming one’s moral character, freeing oneself from demonic oppression, and recovering from illness and incapacity. Moreover, the concept of release is juxtaposed with Jesus’ curative work. Healing encompasses more than just physical aspects; it also represents a state of completeness and liberation from malevolent and societal limitations.¹¹ Luke illustrates the concepts of forgiveness and healing in social contexts, aligning them with their obvious spiritual and bodily implications. In Luke’s perspective, forgiveness is the elimination of the barrier (sin) that previously prevented someone from becoming part of their community. Healing, on the other hand, involves the elimination of a barrier (illness or uncleanness) that has hindered someone from fully participating in their community.¹²

Lord’s acceptable year: Proclaiming Restorative Justice (v. 19)

The phrase “to proclaim the Lord’s acceptable year” does not refer to the season of retributive justice described in Isaiah, which also mentions “the vengeance of our God.” When Luke borrowed the LXX version of Isaiah 61:1-2, he left out the significant line “the day of vengeance of our God” (Isaiah 62:2) and, instead included the descriptive phrase “to send forth the oppressed in release”

11 Patrick E. Spenser, *Rhetorical Texture and Narrative Trajectories of the Lukan Galilean...*, 89.

12 Joel B. Green, *The Theology of the Gospel of Luke...*, 102.

from Isaiah 58:6. This is done to suppress any potential emphasis on the idea of punishment and judgement to create a structure in the citation that resembles that of Lukan.¹³ This refers to the era of Jesus and the upcoming method of salvation that will be restorative in nature. The phrase “acceptable year of the Lord” is a reference to the Jubilee year described in Leviticus 25:1-10. The Jubilee year is a period of freedom and the official declaration of liberation. The people, those who are in positions of power should carry the responsibility of safeguarding the belongings of the people. Hence, the Jubilee publication constitutes a deliberate assault on people in positions of authority who exploit the legal system and impose suffering on the underprivileged for their own benefit. The land is restored to its initial owners, and all debts are forgiven.¹⁴ All individuals have the opportunity to reunite with their relatives. Consequently, during the Jubilee year, a complete reorganisation of society occurs. This reconstruction entails the reinstatement of individuals who are feeble, susceptible, and disadvantaged. According to Walter Brueggemann, the Old Testament Jubilee is seen as a divine order emanating from YHWH, a God who guarantees inheritance and desires to safeguard the weak and vulnerable from the dominance of the powerful and greedy.¹⁵ This Jesus manifesto’ outlines a vision for a complete change in human society, including the emancipation of both repressive and dominant systems and individuals who have become trapped and unaware of the structures they have built. The “acceptable year” of the Lord does not tolerate injustice and revenge but, focuses on the repair of both the victim and perpetrator.

13 John C. Haughey, *Jesus as the Justice of God*, in *The Faith That Does Justice...*, 134.

14 Michael L. Hadley, *Spiritual Foundations of Restorative Justice*, in *Handbook of Restorative Justice: A Global Perspective* (ed. Dennis Sullivan and Larry Tiftt; London: Routledge, 2006), 177.

15 Walter Brueggemann, *Reverberations of Faith: A Theological Handbook of Old Testament Themes* (Louisville: Westminster John Knox Press, 1989), 115.

Effects of Restorative Justice on the Wellbeing of Victims of Criminal Frame-up Cases

Restorative Justice can diminish the intensity of suffering and allow for the commencement of recovery. However, it is crucial to note that it should never be imposed onto anyone without their will. When willingly accepted, it can have profound and lasting impacts on individuals and society. The objective is to pursue Shalom, which encompasses harmony and security for all individuals, by promoting reconciliation and healing as alternatives to seeking retribution and enduring pain. We assert that the pursuit of genuine and fulfilling justice is eternally connected to the spiritual development of all involved individuals.

The prevailing justice system is predominantly shaped by the retributive paradigm. It primarily centres on the perpetrator and disregards the demands, requirements, and negative impact of the crime on the victims, whether imposed by the government or an individual. The purpose of retribution is to ensure that the perpetrator pays for their actions; however, in many circumstances, repayment is not feasible. For example, in instances where individuals are falsely accused, they often suffer irreparable harm to their dignity, reputation, time, livelihood, family, and professional standing. Unfortunately, in many circumstances, the state or system responsible for the injustice is unable to fully compensate for these losses. In the current setting of the media's excessive influence, news about crime spreads swiftly. However, when individuals are proven innocent, the media tends to disregard the story because it is no longer considered newsworthy.¹⁶ Therefore, in such instances, revenge plays a restricted role regarding criminal frame-up situations, victims are often driven by a strong desire for revenge. Retributive

¹⁶ Walter Brueggemann, *Reverberations of Faith: A Theological Handbook of Old Testament Themes...*, 67.

justice does not effectively satisfy resentment. In Luke 4:18–19, it is evident that Jesus views Jubilee justice as a form of justice that restores and repair.

Jesus declared the restoration of the oppressed from systemic oppression. This injustice can be rectified using a restorative approach rather than a retributive one. The “ignored” became the chosen means by which God proclaimed good news. The individual who has been victimised becomes a central part of God’s mission. In contrast to conventional retributive justice, Jesus’ mission did not centre around “victimising” the wrongdoer but rather on empowering those who have been victimised. Luke presents Jesus’ restorative model of justice. The retributive approach to justice has failed to provide a convincing explanation of how punishment and suffering can effectively restore justice. Furthermore, it has not adequately met the victim’s requirements and desires. Restorative justice facilitates the initiation of healing and reparative process for victims and, encourages criminals to express remorse and seek redemption, thus initiating a process of rectifying past injustices. Furthermore, Jesus’ ministry was characterised by the act of granting freedom and liberation.¹⁷ The individuals who are held hostage, oppressed, and unable to see are freed from their state of captivity, oppression, and blindness. Restorative justice primarily prioritises the well-being of the victims while not completely disregarding retribution for the culprits. Similarly, the individuals who were falsely accused and victimised in these situations were under the control of a pervasive injustice that inflicted suffering and torment to benefit a small, privileged group. However, the primary objective of the court system should be the liberation of victims, which can be achieved through an appropriate restorative justice procedure. The “release” was initially declared and initiated by Jesus, but it is now perpetuated by the ecclesia, a collective network of

¹⁷ Ted Grimsrud and Howard Zehr, *Rethinking God, Justice, and Treatment of Offenders...*, 109.

communities.¹⁸ Restorative justice is not a single occurrence, but an ongoing and ever-evolving process that encompasses not only the victim and perpetrator but also several stakeholders such as the community, family, society, government, and ecclesia. Restorative justice assists individuals in transcending arbitrariness of anger, shame, guilt, and other subjective feelings, enabling them to engage in constructive criticism (forgiveness), personal growth, and overall wellness.

False Accusation: The Case of Nambi Narayan

S. Nambi Narayan, a senior scientist in the ISRO cryogenics division, was falsely charged with espionage in 1994 and sentenced to 50 days in prison. The case was closed in 1996 due to a lack of evidence and questionable methods. The Supreme Court declared Narayan not guilty in 1998 and awarded him a compensation of 1 lakh. In 1999, Narayan sought compensation from the National Human Rights Commission for his mental torture. The Kerala government's attitude towards Narayan has been criticized, and the Supreme Court has ordered a committee to consider action against the officials. Narayan believes the government should order a fresh probe and subject the suspect to one-tenth of the torture he experienced.

The Bible provides a restorative justice framework for addressing the consequences of a crime, particularly for victims of wrongful conviction instances. The analysis of Luke 4:18-19 reveals that Jesus, portrayed as the Isaianic figure and a prophet, delivered the message of restorative justice to the impoverished, thereby summarising the narrative and intertextual research. The study has identified "the poor," "captives," "oppressed," and the "blind" as individuals who are victimised by unjust criminal cases and are being treated as objects by the system. Therefore,

¹⁸ Michael L. Hadley, *Spiritual Foundations of Restorative Justice*, in *Handbook of Restorative...*, 90.

it is argued that by engaging in Restorative Justice, individuals can achieve revitalisation and improve their well-being by confronting and addressing structural oppression. The biblical framework of Restorative Justice facilitates the establishment of a fresh moral perspective, where the marginalised individuals are prioritised as focal points from which all other aspects emanate. Jesus' declaration of release was centred on rectifying damage and reinstating tranquillity and concord by empowering the underprivileged through their inclusion in a community. Empowering the victim involve an innovative critique of the wrongdoing, whether systemic or individual, with the aim of restoring, healing, and reconstructing.

14

LITURGY

THEME: THE VOICE OF SILENCE

Ben Das*

Invocation: Folk Song

Call to Worship

“Ascribe to the Lord, O heavenly beings, ascribe to the Lord’s glory and strength. Ascribe to the Lord, the glory of his name; worship the Lord in holy splendour.” (Ps. 29¹⁻²)

Opening Prayer

Loving and gracious God, we come before you to worship you and to magnify your holy name. We seek your presence through worship. Make this moment of worship a time of divine communication. Help us discern the meaning of silence and strengthen us to silence ourselves wherever necessary. Open our hearts and inner eyes to experience and see your glory in this worship. Amen.

Bhajan:

Prayer of Exaltation

L: Let us extol God by a thousand names, God who has neither name nor form.

* Rev. Dr. D. S. Ben Das is Associate Professor in the Department of Religions, and Interim PRO, UTC. He prepared this liturgy and used it for the Sunday Community Worship on 13 - 08 - 2023.

All: God is the God of gods;

God is the Supreme King of the Triad, who create, sustain and destroy the worlds;

God is the *Mūrti*, the manifestation of God, the ancient ancestor, and our parent.

Dear God, "You are the heaven, you are the earth;

You are the wind, you are the light;

The body are you, the soul are You;

Existence, non-existence;

You move dwelling within such

Each one says 'Myself and Mine;'

What shall I call you? How do you render praise?¹

Hail thy flowery feet, Thou transcendent One;

Hail thy roseate feet, Thou immanent One;

Hail thy golden feet, Thou source of life;

Hail thy blossoming feet, Thou be the joy of life;

Hail resplendent blooms of Grace that made us Thine."²

(Manikkavachakar, *Tiruvachakam*)

Thanksgiving Prayer

God, the source of all blessings,

In gratitude, we bow to all generations of ancestors in our blood family.

In gratitude, we bow to all generations of ancestors in our spiritual family.

1 Ratna Navaratnam, *Tiruvachakam: The Hindu Testament of Love* (Bombay: Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, 1963), 231.

2 Ratna Navaratnam, *Tiruvachakam: The Hindu Testament of Love* (Bombay: Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, 1963), 240.

In gratitude, we bow to this land and all the ancestors who made it possible.

In gratitude and compassion, we bow down and transmit our energy to those we love.

(A Buddhist Thanksgiving Prayer)

With gratitude we remember the people, animals, plants, insects, creatures of the sky and sea, air and water, and fire and earth, all whose joyful exertion blesses our life every day.

We, with gratitude, remember the care and labor of a thousand generations of elders and ancestors who have come before us.

We offer our gratitude for the blessings on this earth we have been given.

We offer our gratitude for the measure of health we have been given.

We offer our gratitude for the family and friends we have received.

We offer our gratitude for the community we have been given.

We offer our gratitude for the teachings and lessons we have been given.

We offer our gratitude for the life we have been given.

Amen.

(A Zen Buddhist Thanksgiving Prayer)

Scripture Reading 1: Matthew 26^{57-63a}

⁵⁷Those who had arrested Jesus took him to Caiaphas the high priest, in whose house the scribes and the elders had gathered.

⁵⁸But Peter was following him at a distance, as far as the courtyard of the high priest; and going inside, he sat with the guards in order to see how this would end. ⁵⁹Now the chief priests and the whole council were looking for false testimony against Jesus so that they might put him to death, ⁶⁰but they found none, though

many false witnesses came forward. At last, two came forward ⁶¹and said, “This fellow said, ‘I am able to destroy the temple of God and to build it in three days.’” ⁶²The high priest stood up and said, “Have you no answer? What is it that they testify against you?” ⁶³But Jesus was silent.

Special Song:

Scripture Reading 2: Bhagavad Gīta 2¹⁻⁹

¹Sañjaya said: Madhusūdāna, addressed the following words to Arjuna, who was overwhelmed with compassion and in deep distress and whose eyes were flooded with tears of despondence. ²Srī Bhagavān said: Arjuna, how has this affliction overtaken you at this off hour? It is shunned by noble souls; neither could it bring heaven nor fame to you. ³O Pārtha, yield not to cowardice. It does not befit you. Cast off this petty faint-heartedness and wake up, O vanquisher of foes. ⁴Arjun said: O slayer of Madhu, and slayer of foes, how shall I fight Bhīṣma and Droṇa, with arrows, on the battlefield? Both of them are worthy of our worship. ⁵Better to live on alms in this world than, to slay these noble elders, because after killing them we can only enjoy blood-stained pleasure in, the form of wealth and sense-objects. ⁶We do not know which is meritorious for us, to fight or not to fight, nor do we know whether, we shall win or they will conquer us. The sons of Dhṛtarāṣṭra, by killing whom we do not even wish to live, are arrayed against us. ⁷My nature is overwhelmed by the vice of faint-heartedness, and my mind is confused with regard to my duty. I entreat you, tell me what’s going to be good for me. I am your disciple. Do instruct me, who have taken refuge, in you. ⁸Even on obtaining undisputed sovereignty and an affluent kingdom on this earth as well as lordship over the gods in heaven; I do not see any remedy that can remove my grief, which withers my senses. ⁹O scorcher of enemies, after addressing the indwelling lord thus, Arjuna, the conqueror of sleep, said to Him, “I will not fight,” and became silent.

Reflection:**Confession of Sins**

Loving God, although you have taught us that “One who does my work and looks upon Me as his/her goal, he/she who worships Me without other attachments and who is without hatred towards any creature – he/she comes to Me,” (*Bhagavad Gīta*), often we failed to do so.

Compassionate God, though you have taught us: “The way to the other world does not shine for the ignorant person who blunders, ever deluded by the glamour of wealth. ‘This is the world, and there is no other,’ he/she thinks, and this he/she fails again and again, my sway”, we were misled by the glamour of the world. (*Katha Upaniṣad*)

Although it is told: “Whatever offering or gift is made, whatever austerity is practiced, whatever rite is performed – if it is done without faith, it is called ‘*Asat*,’ we confess that most of us failed to do them with faith. (*Bhagavad Gīta* XVII.28)

Dear God, we confess our failure in meaningfully observing salience in our lives. Though we know that your might manifests through your silence, we have been trying to show our might through voices and noises of many kinds.

All: We are false; our minds are false; our love is also false; yet, if we weep, shall these sinners not attain You?
(Manikkavachakar, *Tiruvachakam*)

Assurance of Pardon

L: Set aside all rules of *dharma* and, come unto Me alone for shelter. Do not grieve. I will release thee from all sins.
(*Bhagavad Gīta*)

Having pardoned of our sins, be assured that those whose sins are destroyed and whose doubts are removed, whose minds are disciplined, and who rejoice in the good of all beings – such holy people attain the beatitudes of God.

(Bhagavad Gīta V.25)

All: We did not deserve anything better. Turley, we were false; but when You, with gentle glance, bade us come, our sufferings creased.
(Manikkavachakar, Tiruvachakam)

Intercessory Prayers

L: Dear sisters and brothers, let us pray for all those who are deprived and suffer in their bodies, minds and spirits.

(Silent Prayer)

L: We shall pray for the world, particularly India, for its peace, harmony, and religious diversity.

(Silent Prayer)

L: Let us pray for those who face heartbreaking turmoil in Manipur.

(Silent Prayer)

L: Let us pray for each UTC community member.

(Silent Prayer)

L: Let us pray for our personal needs.

(Silent Prayer)

All: Amen.

Closing Hymn:

Closing Prayer

“I am going to send an angel in front of you, to guard you on the way, and to bring you to the place that I have prepared. Be attentive to him and listen to his voice; do not rebel against him, for he will not pardon your transgression; for my name is in him. But if you listen attentively to his voice and do all that I say, then I will be an enemy to your enemies and a foe to your foes.” (Ex. 23²⁰⁻²²)

Dear God, the day is coming to its end; we have entered into the hours of darkness. Lead us with your light, in the world of challenges and opportunities. Thank you for speaking to and listening us throughout the worship. Help us work silently rather than making noise and doing nothing. Let the voice of our silence be heard vehemently to challenge the destructive structures and strengthen ourselves. As we depart from this place of worship, come with us and throughout this week. Amen.

Benediction

May God bless us all with success, health, happiness, patience, and strength.

May all our dreams come true, and may we love the life we have always dreamed of.

May God bless us with victory in this life and in our eternal life. Amen.

(A Muslim Benediction)

Membership Fee:

Annual Membership Fee	Rs. 100/-
-----------------------	-----------

Life Membership Fee	Rs. 3000/-
---------------------	------------

MASIHI SEVAK SUBSCRIPTION FORM

I..... hereby pay/renew my Annual subscription for Masihi Sevak for the year..... by Cheque/Draft/M.O. in favour of the United Theological College

Rs..... in words (.....)

Name:.....

(in block letters)

Address:.....

.....

.....

.....

Pin Code:.....

Signature

NEW SUBSCRIPTION RATES

(From 2017 onwards)

India (General)	Rs.	200/-
UTC Alumni (in India)	Rs.	150/-
UTC Students	Rs.	100/-
Oversear by airmail	US\$	40/-

Send this form to:

The Public Relations Office
United Theological College
63, Millers Road,
Benson Town,
Bengaluru - 560 046.

Editorial	v
I. Articles	
1. The Web of Life: Psalm 104's Portrayal of Ecological Interdependence in the Anthropocene Era <i>Mede Jeevan Sagar</i>	1
2. The Nature and Calling of the Church in India Today <i>Ben Jonathan Immanuel</i>	11
3. John Wesley Theology of Covenant: A Foundation for Servant Living <i>F. Lal Chhandama</i>	23
4. Divine Empathy and Human Apathy: The Case of Jonah <i>P D Sengvaidam Chiru</i>	35
5. Mindful Faith: Integrating Mindfulness into Christian Counselling <i>Akhil A O</i>	43
6. Vulnerability of Sexually Abused Children: Analysis of Just Therapy <i>Rita Rana</i>	51
7. Characteristics of Adolescent Girls: Implications for Pastoral Care and Counselling <i>L. Anitha</i>	59
II. Biblical Reflections and Sermons	
8. Worship that Transforms: A Call to Authenticity and Reverence <i>Sam T Rajkumar</i>	67
9. Nathaniel, An Enlightened Person: A Reflection based on John 1:44-51 <i>Johnson Thomaskutty</i>	79
10. Sermon on the Mount as a Key to Understanding Jesus' Social Teachings and Social Justice as a Christian Duty <i>Jeeva Kumar Ravela</i>	85
11. Prophetic Imagination of the Self: Reflection from Isaiah 11: 1-5; Matthew 8: 28-34 <i>Eyingbeni Humtsoe-Nienu</i>	95
12. Jesus, the Prophet <i>Ben Das</i>	101
13. The Impact of Restorative Justice on the Welfare of Victims of Criminal False Accusation Cases: An Examination of Luke 4:18-19 <i>Praveen Kodyattil</i>	109
III. Liturgy	
14. Liturgy - Theme: The Voice of Silence <i>Ben Das</i>	121

THE UNITED THEOLOGICAL COLLEGE

63, Miller's Road, Benson Town, Bengaluru - 560 046, India.
 Phone : 080-2333 2844 / 3438 / 0502, Fax : 080-2333 0015
 E-mail : masihisevak@gmail.com | www.utcbangalore.org